

EDUCATION FOR SENIORS IN EUROPE

Educational practices produced in the framework of the
„Educational Senior Network“ Strategic partnership in adult
education for broadening education of seniors
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• Cooperation partners

• Project partners

Other institutions included in the project: EFOS (European Federation of Older Students in Universities) and its members from Berliner Akademie für weiterbildende Studien e.V., Berlin, Germany; U3A Bytom, Poland; Dresdner Seniorenakademie Wissenschaft und Kunst, Dresden, Germany; Department of Generations Graz University, Austria; Universität Wien, Austria; Uniwersytet Wroclawski, Wroclaw, Poland.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Demographic ageing is too often perceived negatively and older people are sometimes considered a burden on society and on public budgets. A change of attitude is needed to achieve an inclusive society and support, greater solidarity and cooperation with the older generation. The rapid development of the Universities of the Third Age (UTAs) throughout the world is a testimony of their growing importance within our modern societies. The Universities of the Third Age are organisations that provide education and activities mainly for retired people. Study programmes offered to older students are organised on university premises with the participation of university staff and teachers or offered by other institutions and groups of active elderly. In our civic society there are other groups of seniors in communities, residential homes and rural areas not involved in learning. Therefore it is necessary to integrate these groups of seniors into the learning activities by contacting them, doing interviews and preparing innovations of the UTA programmes or by establishing new programmes for new groups of older persons.

For the period of December 1st 2014 to October 30th 2017 there was an approval given for a new Erasmus+ project entitled "Educational Senior Network" (EduSenNet), coordinated by the Comenius University in Bratislava and shared by European Universities and their UTAs in the category KA2 (Key Action 2) entitled '*Strategic partnership for Adult learning*'.

The EduSenNet project aims to identify both the specific needs of older learners aged over 50 and the conditions under which they learn. The project examines opportunities for innovation of the learning programmes, how they can be implemented and by whom.

An identification of the learning environment can assist us in the innovation of the programme not only in urban but also in rural areas and specific communities.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The following two theories are aimed to help the reader to understand:

- What sort of survey is carried out in the EduSenNet – project; why and for whom (*Action research*)
- What sort of frames/obstacles or possibilities there are for seniors to take part in learning activities (*Frame factor theory*)

Action Research

Very often what is called action research are studies carried out in the course of an activity or occupation, typically in the field of education to improve the methods and approach of those involved.

In Wikipedia it is described in those words:

“Action research is either research initiated to solve an immediate problem or a reflective process of progressive problem solving led by individuals working with others in teams or as part of a "community of practice" to improve the way they address issues and solve problems” (<https://en.wikipedia.>)

Action research is a form of collective self-reflective enquiry undertaken by participants in social situations in order to improve the rationality and justice of their own social or educational practices, as well as their understanding of those practices and the situations in which the practices are carried out.

Participatory action research (PAR) has emerged in recent years as a significant methodology for intervention, development and change within communities and groups. It is now promoted and implemented by many international development agencies and university programs, as well as many local community organizations around the world. PAR builds on the critical pedagogy put forward by Paulo Freire as a response to the traditional formal models of education where the “teacher” stands at the front and “imparts” information to the “students” who are passive recipients. This was further developed in adult education models throughout Latin America.

Practitioners who engage themselves in action research inevitably find it to be an empowering experience. It has been useful in many countries as a part of development work e.g. in Namibia (Odin -95)

Diagram 1: Action Research

Frame Factor Theory

In designing modern education different strategies have been used and researched on. Urban Dahllöv was one of the researchers who quite early stressed the importance of not only looking at the teaching/learning process itself but also to look at the frames in terms of time allocated, organisation of learning situations and other frame factors to understand and explain the outcomes.

Later followers to Dahllöv have stressed the importance for educational researchers to bridge the gap between micro- and macro studies and to do it with due regard both to the frame conditions surrounding the actors and to the complexities of the processes involved.

The theories about the phenomena outlined above do vary with the problem and its context, but they have in each case been inspired by the same basic model “the frame factor theory”.

Gunnar Berg has from the frame factor theory developed what he refers to as a “Free space model” where he is stressing that there are certain frames like laws, rules and regulations, resources and time available etc. These frames constitutes the “outer boundaries” for what is possible. But through empirical studies he could also identify an “inner boundary” which

has more to do with how people think about their free space of possibilities to act in different ways.

Outer boundary

Diagram 2: The free space model

U3As are not strictly regulated by laws and state grants/resources but we can still use the frame factor thinking and the “free space model” to understand why people answer the way they do to the questionnaire in our survey.

How do they look upon their frames and possibilities for taking part in education activities – where are their “inner boundaries” and what constitutes these boundaries. With the help of those theories and models we might come closer in our understanding of the answers to the questionnaires.

3. PROJECT METHODOLOGY, WORKING PROCESS

Objectives, needs and outcomes have been met in various ways:

- by summarising experiences;
- by encouraging the elderly to take part in learning activities;
- by developing their interest in learning through participation in activities designed to promote and extend their knowledge and skills.

It was necessary to examine the objectives and motivation for and barriers to learning of the elderly persons taking part in the programmes as well of those who do not participate. The introduction of the new programmes and the upgrading of the old ones could involve the elderly in activities more suited to their needs.

The project research was based on a questionnaire survey with the purpose of encouraging older people to take part in learning activities. The project teams gave them information about learning programmes and they opened space to create appropriate activities. In the groups of the elderly students at the universities and academies the project partners focused on the motivation for and barriers to study activities, wishes, requirements and proposals for the future. The research into the learning needs and conditions with the comparison of the results became the basis for the curriculum innovation within the study programmes.

The project goals were achieved and they are documented in the Review. The table presenting the learning possibilities revealed in the study, facilitated the validation of non-formal and informal learning and its recognition within formal programmes. The project activities gave a chance for improvement of the quality of life of the isolated older people, for the use of the knowledge potential of the older students within communities and regions and for the support of the learning needs of the elderly in general.

The project plan was divided into three phases with organizing 6 project meetings, a project conference and project activities. The project plan included the work on the Study about learning possibilities, the setup of the Review table with the comparison and evaluation of the collected data. The second phase was aimed at the work with the questionnaires focusing on the older persons generally as well as on the elderly students specifically. The third phase of the project focused on the qualitative and quantitative analyses with the design of new innovative study programmes and learning methods.

The Project teams and the elderly students were directly involved in the project. They carried out the research by means of questionnaires and

interviews with older people in communities and in rural areas. The project managers in each country utilised many project methods as the collection of the data, summary of the results and their evaluation, comparison of the results from different countries and among the project teams, description of the project ways of working and work practices. The project meetings included not only presentations of the results, discussions and exchanges of the findings but also round tables, meetings with the students and the practical training of the moderators involved in the project.

The project website <http://edusennet.efos-europa.eu> is one of the most important dissemination tools besides the project newsletters, flyer and personal presentations at conferences abroad.

4. WHAT SORT OF RESEARCH WE HAVE DONE

In the Review table we present the Study about the learning possibilities for the elderly students in the 12 chosen universities.

The Survey about the motivation, barriers and wishes of the elderly consists of the opinions of both the older persons and the elderly students. The results were obtained from questionnaires, interviews, personal visits and discussions within the groups of 930 respondents of older people from 7 countries and of 3,151 respondents of elderly students from 7 universities and 6 countries.

The communities of the elderly were contacted in residential homes, in rural areas where there are some transport limits or long distances to university campuses. Therefore the new curricula and study programmes based on the project findings were designed for the chosen groups of the elderly. New offers in a new environment were designed for the new groups of the elderly to give them a possibility for learning in their later life.

For the older students innovative study programmes were developed according to their needs, proposals and the evaluation of the project

research. All these efforts led to the enlargement and widening of the study programmes of the universities for the older generation and to the encouragement of learning of the elderly. On the other side, they led the university management to serious research work focusing on the older generation to forward the promotion of active ageing by learning.

4.1. Project outcomes

- Review Table presenting the learning possibilities revealed in the study;
- Improvement in the quality of life of isolated older people, support their learning needs;
- Research into learning needs and conditions, comparison of the results;
- Curriculum innovation within the study programmes;
- Facilitating the validation of non-formal and informal learning and its recognition within formal programmes;
- A project booklet and Newsletters setting out the results gained from the project analyses;
- Use of the knowledge potential of the older students within communities and regions.

5. REVIEW TABLE AS A RESULT OF THE PROJECT EduSenNet

Survey among EduSenNet project partners and EFOS member institutions

October 2014 – May 2015

Simultaneously with the application for the EduSenNet project, EFOS started in the autumn of 2014 a survey among its members about the present situation in the education of older people. After the start of EduSenNet in December 2014 the collection of data was completed, compiled and evaluated. The result is displayed below.

The results of the present survey form the basis for the further activities in the context of the EduSenNet project focusing on key aspects of future developments in the education for older people. The Project consists of two groups – the project partners and a group of EFOS members not included in the project. Further results arising from this survey are published in other chapters.

5.1. Evaluation

Respondents:

EduSenNet project partners

- Comenius University in Bratislava / Centre for Continuing Education (Slovakia)
- Uppsala Senioruniversitet (Sweden)
- Otto-von-Guericke-Universität, Magdeburg (Germany)
- Seniorenkolleg an der TU Chemnitz (Germany)
- Senioren Academie Groningen-Friesland-Drenthe, Groningen (the Netherlands)
- University of the Third Age - Brno University of Technology, Brno (Czech Republic)
- Universidad Permanente de la Universidad de Alicante (Spain)

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Other EFOS members included into the project

- Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Uniwersytet Trzeciego Wieku, Wrocław (Poland)
- Österreichische Hochschülerinnen- und Hochschülergesellschaft Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz (Austria)
- EFOS, Wien (Austria)
- Freunde und Förderer der Dresdner Seniorenakademie Wissenschaft und Kunst, Dresden (Germany)
- Berliner Akademie für weiterbildende Studien e.V., Berlin (Germany)

University Background

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
Established in (year)	Bratislava 1990	Uppsala 1979	Magdeburg 1993	Chemnitz 1993	Groningen 1986	Brno 2000	Alicante 1999
How do you define 'older student'?	40+, 50+, secondary education	People above 58	People above 40	above 65/67 seniors college open for all ages	People above 50	People above 50, secondary education	People above 50

	Poland	Austria		Germany	
Established in (year)	Wroclaw 1976	Graz 1945	Wien 1994	Dresden 1994	Berlin 1985
How do you define 'older student'?	No age limit for study	Women above 40, Men above 45	Women above 40, Men above 45	People above 65	Older citizens, interested in further education

Table 1: *University background 1*

- We see a wide variety in organisations for academic education for older people.
- The definition of an 'older student' varies also, with (lower) age limits from 40 to 65. Remarkable is the differentiation in the starting age for women (40) and men (45) in Graz and Wien.
- Wroclaw and Berlin don't apply any age limit. Chemnitz stipulates an age limit but doesn't apply it in practice.

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Part of or linked to a university / institution	Full part	Linked	Full part	Full part	Linked	Linked	Full part
Name of university / Institution	Comenius University in Bratislava / Centre for Continuing Education	University of Uppsala	Otto-von-Guericke-Universität	University of Technology Chemnitz	Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, Hanzehogeschool Groningen, Stenden Hogeschool	Brno University of Technology	University Alicante
Number of fulltime/part-time students per semester	PT 1887	PT 2600	PT 586	PT 800	PT 1800	PT 2201	PT 1300
Pre-qualifications required	secondary education	none	none	none	none	secondary education	none
Duration of study / Course	2 - 3 years	no time limit	1 semester	1 semester	5 -10 weeks	1 semester/ 2 semester	free choice by annual offer

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Cost, fees Contributions	€ 75 for working people € 65 for retirees per year =2 semesters	€ 25 and € 30-80 per semester for lectures series and work groups	€ 50 per semester. For special courses € 10 - 25 Max. € 50	€ 35 per semester lectures , Courses PC € 30	€ 102-202 per course	€ 14 - 33 depending on the type of course	€ 65 per course; each course has 40 hours

Table 2: University background 2

	Poland	Austria		Germany	
	Wroclaw	Graz	Wien	Dresden	Berlin
Part of or linked to a university / institution	Full part	Linked	Linked	Linked	Linked
Name of university / institution	Uniwersytet Wroclawski	Karl-Franzens Universität Graz	Alma Mater Rudolphina – Universität Wien	TU Dresden, Musikhochschule Carl Maria von Weber, Deutsches Hygienemuseum, Staatliche Kunstsammlungen.	Freie Universität Berlin, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Technische Universität Berlin, Universität der Künste Berlin

	Wroclaw	Graz	Wien	Dresden	Berlin
Number of fulltime/part-time students per semester	FT 765	FT/PT 1957	FT 5582 PT 96	PT 750	PT 500
Pre-qualifications required	none	University level	Abitur, university entrance exam	none	none
Duration of study / Course	none (it could be up to the end of the life)	up to 8 semesters, according to the specific studies leading to BA and MA	according to the discipline of study, 8-12 semesters	free choice by semester offer	1 semester 1 Sommeruni week
Cost, fees Contributions	100 zl.(ca. € 25) per year	€ 18 per semester	€ 20 per semester	€ 40 per semester	€ 50 for Sommeruni

Table 3: *University background 3*

- All institutes have a link of some sort with one or more universities and/or other institutes for higher education. Only the UTAs of Wroclaw, Magdeburg, Bratislava and Alicante are an integral part of the university.
- Only Wroclaw, Graz and Wien state that they have fulltime students. In Graz and Wien these fulltime students carry out a regular academic study. In Wroclaw they attend special courses for seniors.
- Wien has by far the most senior students, but the majority of them are between the age of 40 and 55.

Age range

	< =50	51 - 65	66 - 70	71 - 75	76+
Uppsala	0	120	705	1050	725
Magdeburg	0	127	149	175	126
Chemnitz	0	100	500	100	100
Groningen	4	869	1285	679	615
Alicante	10	581	384	200	125
Dresden	5	152	176	246	172
Berlin	20	60	300	80	40

	< =60	61-70	71-80	81-90	91+
Wroclaw	95	379	263	31	3

	< =50	51 - 65	66 - 75	76+
Brno	0	438	1431	311

	<= 50	51 - 65	66+
Bratislava	10	772	1105

	40 - 55	55+
Graz	1541	406
Wien	3987	1691

Table 4: Age range

- In most of the institutes the peak lies between 66 and 75 years. The remarkable exceptions are Alicante, on the one hand, with a notably younger population (peak 51 - 65 years) and Magdeburg and Dresden, on the other hand, with a notably older population (peak 71 - 75 years).
- When we compare category 65+ the oldest population of students over 65 is in Uppsala 95.5% and in Chemnitz 87.5%.
- Graz and Wien clearly have a different population of senior students, with the majority below the age of 65. Some institutes used different age intervals, making a direct comparison difficult.

Types of studies *

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Formal / non-formal	non-formal	non-formal	non-formal	non-formal	non-formal	non-formal
Integrated / separate	integrated, separate	separate	integrated, separate	separate	separate	separate
Certificate	yes	no	no	no	yes / no	yes

	Poland	Austria		Germany	
	Wroclaw	Graz	Wien	Dresden	Berlin
Formal / non-formal	non-formal	formal	formal, non-formal	non-formal	non-formal
Integrated / separate	separate	integrated	integrated	Integrated	separate
Certificate	no	yes	yes	no	no

Table 5: Types of studies

*

formal

informal

integrated

separated

= education certified by the government, with diploma and/or academic title

= education not certified by government, e.g. attendance at university lectures without formal

exam; special courses or studies for seniors

= younger and older students study together

= special studies for older students

- Only in Austria formal studies at the university are listed under education for older people.
- The separated education is slightly favoured.
- Certificates are not a common instrument among the respondents. Graz, Wien, Brno, Bratislava and Alicante are the exceptions.
- In Graz and Wien, where senior students attend regular studies, a completed study leads to a degree.
- Brno, Bratislava and Alicante issue certificates for special courses for seniors.

Figure 1: Interest of the students in the subjects of study

- Everywhere humanities are well represented. At Technical Universities natural sciences play a more dominant role than at general universities.
- Graz, Wien and Chemnitz could not answer.
- Probably, most of the respondents had to apply some mathematical tricks to produce the requested data
- Lectures and workshops are most common.
- Activities with young people (intergenerational) are not popular.
- Most of the respondents offer an educational programme with a great variety of learning and teaching methods.

6. FEASIBILITY STUDY OF THE PROJECT EduSenNet

Survey among the elderly - non students

2015 - 2016

6.1. Evaluation

Coordinators of the survey:

EduSenNet partners

- Comenius University in Bratislava / Centre for Continuing Education (Slovakia)
- Uppsala Senioruniversitet (Sweden)
- Otto-von-Guericke-Universität, Magdeburg (Germany)
- Seniorenkolleg an der TU Chemnitz (Germany)
- Senioren Academie Groningen-Friesland-Drenthe, Groningen (Netherlands)
- University of the Third Age - Brno University of Technology, Brno (Czech Republic)
- Universidad Permanente, de la Universidad de Alicante (Spain)

EduSenNet non project partners

- Dresden (Germany)
- Bytom (Poland)

6.1.1. Personal data

Respondents	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Chemnitz 109	Groningen 135	Brno 227	Alicante 103
Total: 878							
Living place							
In a town/city	70%	80%	70.8%	22.9%	38%	85%	55.34%
In a village / country	30%	20%	29.2%	30.3%	51%	15%	44.66%
In another town	0%	0%	0%	43.1%	11%	0%	0%
Housing	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Alone in own flat / house	17.44%	10%	28.6%	41.3%	22%	37%	19.42%
With family	49.54%	19%	71.4%	57.8%	63%	59%	55.34%
Residential home	31.20%	68%	0%	0%	10%	1%	25.24%
Other forms of housing	1.82%	3%	0%	0.9%	5%	3%	0%

Table 6: Personal data of the elderly from different communities and countries 1

During the project work we have contacted communities of the elderly in many different places and towns mentioned in a survey.

- In the group from Uppsala 100% of the respondents are of Swedish nationality but 9% of them are born in another country, mainly in Finland, and most of them came to Sweden as a child of refugees during the Second World War.
- Chemnitz: The geographical distribution of the respondents shows, that 22.9% live in urban areas with > 50,000 inhabitants (“in a town/city”) and 43.1% with < 50,000 inhabitants (“in another town”). 30.3% live in rural areas with villages under 10,000 inhabitants (“in a village/country”).
- In Alicante 55.34% of non-retired respondents live in relatively large cities or towns with more than 100,000 inhabitants.
- In Groningen 38% respondents live in a town or city with an institution for higher education for older people (i.e. Senioreen Academie). Only 11% live in another town.
- Approximately 2/3 of the respondents are (F) female. Only in Brno and Groningen the number is slightly smaller (*Table 7*.)
- For most partners the biggest group of the respondents is between 61 and 70 years.
- In Uppsala the biggest group of the respondents is between 71 and 80 years. Two respondents were more than 90 years old.
- Only Magdeburg and Chemnitz extended their questionnaire with an age group ‘under 50’. (*Table 7*.)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Your Gender / Your Age	M: 35.78% F: 64.22%	M: 36% F: 64%	M: 38.8% F: 61.2%	M: 37.6% F: 62.4%	M: 42% F: 58%	M: 45% F: 55%	M: 38.83% F: 61.17%
Under 50	0%	0%	6.1%	1.8%	0%	0%	0%
50 – 60	19.27%	2%	12.2%	11%	11%	18%	15.53%
61 – 70	49.54%	23%	73.5%	39.4%	44%	45%	39.81%
71 – 80	25.69%	50%	6.1%	36.7%	34%	32%	28.16%
81+	5.5%	25%	2.0%	11%	11%	5%	16.5%
Physical handicap	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Yes	13.76%	11%	/	2.8%	10%	3%	25.24%
No	86.24%	89%	/	84.4%	90%	97%	74.76%
No response				12.8 %			

Table 7: Personal data of the elderly from different communities and countries 2

- Magdeburg: Physical handicap was not part of the questionnaire. In Chemnitz 12.8% no response.
- The respondents mention the following physical handicaps: Orthopaedic illnesses / disabilities / arthritis / osteoporosis; Heart diseases, shortness of breath; Deafness, poor eyesight.

Education	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Primary	7.34%	13%	2.0%	11.9%	1%	2%	34.95%
Secondary	52.3%	19%	28.6%	24.8%	16%	46%	27.18%
University	39.45%	65%	69.4%	58.7%	74%	50%	23.3%
Others	0.91%	3%	0%	4.6%	9%	2%	14.56%

Table 8: Personal data of the elderly from different communities and countries 3

- For this part it is important to know that for a study at the UTA of Comenius University in Bratislava an educational prequalification at secondary school level is requested. The same applies to Brno.
- The other partners don't ask for prequalification.
- In Alicante the large number of respondents in the primary school group is remarkable.
- A group of – "Others" – has a complete different level, which is related to their professional studies or medium-level vocational training certifications of a technical nature.
- Except for Bratislava and Alicante, most of the respondents have an university education.

6.1.2. Learning

B.1. Do you think learning in later life is important and are you interested in taking part in learning activities?
(Table 9, Figure 2)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Groningen 135	Brno 227	Alicante 103
Yes	73.4%	77%	100%	93%	90%	88.35%
No	26.6%	23%	0%	7%	10%	11.65%
No response	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

YES: The majority of the respondents think that learning in later life is important. Reasons for taking part in learning activities are very similar for all the respondents.

See below some comments of the respondents from Chemnitz which corresponded with the answers from other interviewees:

- it slows the aging process, stimulates brain activity;
- to be able to cope better with everyday life;
- to be able to maintain previous life independently as long as possible;
- to understand technical progress (dealing with new appliances and new media, computer, mobile phone);
- to develop oneself, to have joy and fun with new things and topics;
- to continue to be actively involved in social life;
- to have a say, especially with young generation (children, grandchildren);
- to understand globalization, to gain information (especially about politics and society);
- to maintain one's mental health and curiosity;
- to maintain exchanges with others, meet interesting people.

NO: There are some issues that discourage respondents from becoming involved in learning: from Alicante and other interviewees

- lack of basic skills;
- advanced age and health problems;
- lack of interest;
- cannot take part in learning activities because they have to take care of domestic chores and of their husbands (the role of gender and socio-cultural self-exclusion evidenced by some of the female respondents in Alicante).

B.2. How do you find out about learning possibilities? Where can you find out about learning possibilities?

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Groningen 135	Brno 227	Alicante 103
Friends, family colleagues	60%	21%	86.7%	61%	65%	73.79%
Advertising	8.5%	25%	6.7%	47%	5.8%	9.71%
Internet	30.3%	16%	20%	69%	34%	26.21%
Newspaper	27.5%	25%	15.6%	42%	12.8%	25.24%
TV / Radio	32.1%	6%	2.2%	0%	11.5%	18.45%
Other	2.6%	5%	0%	0%	3%	12.62%
I do not know	3.67%	2%	0%	0%	1.8%	14.56%

Table 10: How / where can you find out about learning possibilities?

- Most of the interviewed persons in Bratislava, Magdeburg, Chemnitz, Brno and Alicante mentioned that “personal contacts” are essential for getting information about learning opportunities.
- In Uppsala “advertising” and “newspaper” are more frequent, both sources have the percentage of 25.
- Social communication networks as “Internet”, especially visible in the group of 50-to-71-years-old respondents in Alicante, play an increasingly important role, also mentioned by the respondents in Groningen (69%), where the participants can be informed via Internet or by other respondents from the project participants.
- In the rural areas in Chemnitz at the meetings in the church, clubs and other social events in citizens centres the elderly people are encouraged to take part in learning activities.
- In Groningen TV/radio was mentioned by none of the respondents.

B.4. Which other learning activities for the over 50s in your region are you familiar with?

- Chemnitz: The interviewed people are familiar with a variety of institutions that offer learning programs for the elderly. Especially the “Volkshochschule”, a German educational institution that offers seminars for a very wide target group, is popular among the population (30.06%). The results of this report will be used for the development of new educational programs for the elderly, to motivate them to take part in learning activities, such as the “Seniors College” at Chemnitz University of Technology. However, civic clubs (22.7%) and university institutions such as the Senior College (20.25%) are well known, but the latter one is not well known in rural areas.
- In Magdeburg, most of the interviewees are familiar with the “Volkshochschule” (97.7%), the Urania (55.8%) and foundations (such as Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung) (34.9 %). Also other learning activities for the over 50s were mentioned: adult education in rural areas, church adult education, Otto-von-Guericke-Society, Club Emeritus, Geschichtsverein des Kulturhistorischen Museums Magdeburg and Studium generale.
- In Bratislava 41.3% of the respondents answered “I do not know”, 19.25% “did not answer”, 13.75% are interested in a foreign language course, 11% are interesting in IT-courses and the others in painting, health education, discussions for pensioners in the Club for senior citizens, etc.
- Brno University of Technology offers IT-courses, foreign language courses, sport courses, dancing courses, health courses, etc.
- In Groningen 62% of the respondents named various learning facilities in the region. 24% answered with none / not applicable, 14 % with blank.
- In Sweden there are a number of organizations that organize learning activities: (in Swedish studieförbund: SPF, PRO, Vuxenskolan, ABF, NBV, Medborgarskolan, Bilda) Senior Universities, Aktiva seniorer, Seniornet. In the countryside PRO is the most frequently mentioned.

Learning facilities mentioned:

- Local welfare organisations: counselling, lectures and courses;
- Social Cultural Work: courses, knowledge-café, Seniorweb and workshops in community centres;
- Libraries and similar institutions (Fryske Academie, Treosar): gathering knowledge, education;
- Open University, 'Volksuniversiteit', 'Vrije Academie': language courses, culture and hobbies;
- University of applied sciences, University Groningen, Senioren Academie, Studium Generale: education of a higher level;
- Local societies: for e.g. women, excursions, exchange of ideas on a variety of interesting subjects;
- Art centres, nature societies: knowledge and experience of art, music and nature;
- Churches: theological and evangelical education.

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In Alicante 93.20% of the interviewees answered this question, these being their most significant answers:

- those which develop collective initiatives (such as Housewives' Associations);
- those promoted by Seniors' Centres or Pensioners' Associations and the Seniors' Home located in the neighbourhood where I live;
- those which are carried out by the Day Care Centre and the ones that the Red Cross Centre promotes;
- those developed by Adult Training and Education Centres. Those performed by CEAMS;
- courses and cultural activities of all kinds organised by the Town Hall;
- those developed by the National Distance Education University and the Permanent University;
- the ones which are organised by private Reading, Poetry and Painting Clubs and up to 18% of the respondents claim that they know NO activities addressed to over-50s.

B.5. Which of these learning activities would be suitable for you?

- Chemnitz: This question has a very high failure rate with 73.39 %. However, among the people who answered that question the “Volkshochschule” is the most popular education institution as well (9.68%), Civic center 6.45%, Senior college 6.45% and Others 4.03%.
- In Brno are IT-courses, foreign language courses, health courses, sport courses, etc.
- It is interesting, that in Bratislava 37.6% of the interviewed persons answered “No” and 33.06% “Did not answer”. The courses, that are suitable for the respondents are IT-courses, foreign language courses, physical activities, UTA, etc.
- In Groningen 60% of the answers to the question B.4. specified the categories: interested in everything, if easily accessible, interested in everything, if on an appropriate level and specific subjects like photography, music, painting, computer and practical activities.
- In Alicante 90.8% of the interviewed persons find activities offered by the bodies, centres and institutions mentioned in B.4. Those of a cultural nature related to Humanities (Writing, Literature, Poetry, Painting, History, Singing, Theatre and Cinema). Many of the respondents want to learn to read and write correctly because they could not do it in the past. The next suitable activities are learning languages and new technologies, or activities related to health, mind and body (Tai Chi, Physical Activity, Nutrition, Psychology for daily life...), as well as cookery, cosmetics and beauty care, dancing and games.
- In Sweden (Uppsala) the most common answers are senior organisations as PRO and SPF. Senior University is mentioned as number three in a ranking list.

B.6. Which of the following do you think are good reasons to take part in learning activities?

(Table 12, Figure 3)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Getting new information	60.6%	35%	97.5%	41.73%	47%	74%	66.02%
Meeting people, new social contacts	48.6%	24%	65.0%	23.55%	10%	41%	58.25%
Overcoming isolation	18.3%	3%	0%	0%	0%	14%	19.42%
Being more active	45.9%	13%	35.0%	0%	17%	36.6%	48.54%
Improving the quality of life	48.6%	24%	17.5%	30.58%	21%	52%	33.01%
Other	3.67%	1%	12.5%	1.24%	5%	1.8%	5.83%
No response	0%	0%	0%	2.89%	0%	0%	0%

- For all the respondents the most important category for the answers are “Finding out about things / getting new information”.
- Very equal results can be found in the three categories “Meeting people and improving social contact”, “Improving the quality of life in retirement” and “Being more active”. In Magdeburg the last two reasons play a secondary role.
- In Groningen the reason – “Overcoming isolation” - was not included in the list of choices.
- In Groningen the questionnaire was adapted in certain aspects to the life circumstances in the Netherlands, in order to make it more accessible for the respondents. The sequence of some of the questions was re-arranged and the list of choices was extended for some of the multiple choice questions. The Dutch version of this report reflects the answers to the Dutch questionnaire. For the English version the report was reworked to correspond with the international (English) questionnaire to make it comparable to the reports of the other partners.

B.7. Would more information and wide range of learning activities persuade you to take part? (Table 13)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Chemnitz 109	Groningen 135	Brno 227	Alicante 103
Yes	76.1%	35%	58.1%	54.2%	48%	83%	72.82%
No	22%	26%	0%	0%	52%	17%	27.18%
Maybe	0.91%	39%	32.3%	0%	0%	0%	0%
No answer/ I don't know	0.91%	0%	9.7%	45.9%	0%	0%	0%

B.8. If yes, which subjects would interest you?

- Chemnitz: The following topics were mentioned:
Foreign languages, Usage of tablets and smartphones (i-Phone), Familiarity with the Internet, Politics and society, social development, Developing of the city and the region, World religions, Philosophy, Foreign countries and cultures, Literature, Technological developments (for example textile technology), Gardening, Cooking, Addictions.
- In Uppsala at the top of the list are languages and literature followed by health, philosophy and religion.
"Lack of political issues".
- In Magdeburg, the same as in Bratislava, Groningen and Brno most frequent answers:

Foreign languages, Psychology, Historical scholarship, Art history, Architecture, Photography, Literature, Sociology, Economy, Medicine, Philosophy, Law, Health care, Environment, Political Science, Theology, History, architecture, civil engineering, Informatics, General/multidisciplinary, Physical activity, Natural Science, Music and theatre, Human relations, Sociology, Economy, Social rights, Tourism and leisure management together with other fields related to ecological farming and the environment, as well as trekking and open-air guided tours to enjoy nature and meditation workshops.

B.9. If no, what would prevent you from taking part? (Table 14, Figure 4)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Chemnitz 109	Groningen 135	Brno 227	Alicante 103
Personal health problem	52.3%	12%	4.3%	15.6%	10.4%	52.4%	32.14%
Partner's health problem	11.9%	4%	0%	4.6%	5.2%	15.9%	3.57%
Lack of spare time	23%	29%	26.1%	10.1%	14.8%	26%	10.71%
Personal commitment (Care of family)	20.1%	8%	17.4%	9.1%	9.6%	22%	14.29%

	Bratislava	Uppsala	Magdeburg	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno	Alicante
Distance from venue	32.1%	7%	8.7%	16.5%	12.6%	17.6%	35.71%
Lack of suitable travel facilities	5.5%	1%	4.3%	0%	5.2%	7.5%	35.71%
Financial problems	20.1%	2%	0%	8.3%	15.6%	20.3%	10.71%
Not enough quality teachers	9.1%	2%	0%	0%	3%	16.3%	0%
Volunteer work	0%	0%	0%	6.4%	0%	0%	0%
Professional activities	0%	0%	0%	3.7%	0%	0%	0%
Other – Sloth	8.3% 1.83%	5%	4.3%	2.8%	0%	4.8%	25%
Nothing	0%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%	59.26%
Work commitment	0%	0%	78.3%	0%	0%	0%	0%
No response	0%	0%	0%	22.9%	0%	0%	0%

B.9

B.10. Which type of education would you prefer? (Table 15, Figure 5)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany		Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Chemnitz 109	Groningen 226	Brno 227	Alicante 103
Lectures	37.6%	46%	83.3%	33.53%	72%	55.51%	60.19%
Seminars	17.4%	15%	62.5%	35.29%	43%	29.08%	29.13%
Excursions	36%	7%	60.4%	18.82%	45%	30.4%	36.89%
Discussions	25.7%	26%	27.1%	0%	27.4%	12.8%	32.04%
Exercises, training	32.1%	5%	25.0%	0%	19.26%	34.3%	40.78%
Project group	0%	0%	22.9%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Other	4.6%	1%	4.2%	2.35%		0.44%	13.59%
No response	0%	0%	0%	10%	0%	0%	0%

B.10

- "Lectures" are the most popular form of education by all the interviewed persons, followed by classical „seminars“ in Magdeburg and Chemnitz. In Groningen the latter is on the third place. In Chemnitz in all lectures a discussion is included.
- In Groningen and Bratislava "excursions" were in the second place. In Magdeburg, Brno and Alicante "excursions" were in the third place. However, the respondents in Chemnitz are willing to attend excursions as long as they are organized in the region.
- In Uppsala the respondents mentioned in the second place "discussions", whereas in Groningen "discussions" and "exercises and training" were chosen less frequently.
- As for the type of education the respondents of Alicante and Brno put "Exercises and training" in the second place.
- In urban areas around Chemnitz new seminars for "newcomer" seniors will be prepared. They have to go to meeting points for the elderly people, where they watch a lecture from the Seniors College in Chemnitz by livestream and afterwards they have discussions with the seniors from the "Seniors College".
- In Magdeburg a circle of interested older people meet in a "project group" (11.9%).
- As for the section named as "Other": in Alicante (13.59%) say that they would enjoy "workshops" and "something active which goes beyond mere listeningwhich catches my attention and motivates me".

B.11. Is the social aspect of learning important for you? (learning inside a group and in a direct contact with the lecturer); How do you prefer to learn? (Chemnitz) (Table 16, Figure 6)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Chemnitz 109	Groningen 135	Alicante 103
Yes	73.4%	58%	59.2%	41.26%	71%	96.12%
No	26.6%	42%	16.3%	49.65%	29%	3.88%
I do not know	0%	0%	24.5%	0%	0%	0%
No response	0%	0%	0%	6.29%	0%	0%
Other	0%	0%	0%	2.8%	0%	0%

B.12. Would you like to use new media for learning either at home or in a group (e.g. courses on cd, live transmission of lectures via internet) (Table 17, Figure 7)

	Slovakia	Sweden	Germany	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Spain
	Bratislava 109	Uppsala 146	Magdeburg 49	Chemnitz 109	Groningen 135	Alicante 103
Yes	28.4%	47%	36.7%	13.99%	60%	45.63%
No	55%	53%	40.8%	86.01%	40%	54.37%
I do not know	16.5%	0%	22.4%	0%	27%	0%

- Only in Groningen the majority of the respondents (60%) said “Yes” as they see new media in education for the elderly people an important tool for expanding their knowledge, exchanging experience and getting new information from more subjects, “it enables them to have access to exhibitions, music, cinema and a huge number of art and literature resources, as well as news without leaving home; and at a low cost or completely free of charge”.
- The others mentioned that they would like to learn and manage new tools and innovative learning formats, but they need help from people, who can teach them how to follow activities on the Internet or multimedia resources.
- The other respondents said “No”, with the argument that the communication face to face with a real contact is essential. The internet is perceived only as a supplement. Or they are very old, or to learn new technologies will be complicated.

B.13. What sort of measure comes to your mind that would make it easier for you to take part in learning?

The respondents were asked to mention what measures they thought might make it easier to take part in learning activities. Here are the answers without any order:

- Short distance to the learning venue, better transport (public/private) facilities, good accessibility of the place of learning; Location-based services, learning opportunities in the home town or residential area;
- Free and low-cost learning opportunities, better financial situation, cheaper courses, lower fees;
- Accessibility and facilities which match the special needs of disabled persons for lectures and seminar rooms (comfortable seating in case of orthopaedic disorders, hearing amplification in the auditorium);
- Senior friendly learning environment; attend lectures together with friends, pleasant atmosphere;
- Teachers-instructors must be aware of the type of audience they are addressing, and they must use the pedagogy, methodology and empathy required to deal with these seniors and train them properly;
- Home tutor and an opportunity to have learning material; quality of equipment, access to the Internet;
- Extending and adapting the training activities also in small towns and villages; additionally conceived

- for small groups (15 people) who can be given a personal treatment; appropriate duration of courses;
- Overcome access barriers; a need exists to establish close collaboration schemes between social agents, public-private institutions and communities of citizens and older users in order to adapt the offer, to extend it and to provide it with the necessary formative services suited to the diverse realities that characterise life of today's seniors (comment from Alicante).

B.14. If you are not involved in educational activities, what other activities and recreational activities do you practice? (Table 18)

	Slovakia	Germany	Netherlands	Czech Republic
	Bratislava	Chemnitz	Groningen	Brno
Reading books	68%		74%	63%
Gardening	50%		32%	52%
Babysitting	15%		14%	24%
Singing, dancing, musical, sport activities	18%		17%	7%
Art activities, handiwork	11%		20%	10%
Volunteering	8%	41.3%	36%	5.3%
Travelling	40%		32%	46%
Other	11%	58.7%	54%	19%

We do not have answers from all the project partners, but as we can see, the most recreational activities were: reading, gardening, travelling and in Groningen and Chemnitz also volunteering more than in Bratislava and Brno.

6.2. CONCLUSIONS

CONCLUSIONS – Alicante

The survey was administered in neighbourhoods located on the outskirts of Alicante Town (with 55.34% of interviewees) and small municipalities and rural areas (the remaining 44.66%). In any case, these are areas where we have worked with the survey in: a) seniors' associations which carry out leisure and free-time activities (usually in Pensioners' Centres and Homes and regional houses or centres); b) Municipal Community Social Centres; c) Preventive Care Centres for seniors: CEAMS and CIMS; d) Third-Age Homes and Day Care Centres; and e) Residents' and Housewives' Associations.

The predominant gender is female (61.17% of those who answered) and the prevailing age group is the one going from 61 to 70 years of age (39.81%), followed by another significant group –71-to-80-year-olds– that accounts for 28.16% of interviewees. It is additionally worth highlighting that the 81+ group (with 16.50%) slightly exceeds that of 50-to-60-year-olds (15.53%) –the involvement shown by this group of individuals of a more advanced age in our survey being highly significant.

These are older adult citizens who up to a percentage of 55.34% live in their own house or apartment/flat with their family; and the proportion of those who live in a pensioners'/old age home (25.24%) is above that of those living alone (only 19.42%); finally, up to 25.24% claim to have health problems which prevent them from following or being able to carry out formative activities.

The majority of this interviewed population has either Primary studies (34.95%) or Secondary ones (27.18%), and up to 88.35% recognise that training for learning in later life is important and show an interest in taking part in learning activities.

73.79% of our respondents say that the knowledge about possible formative activities reaches them through friends, relatives and colleagues –it is also worthy of mention that according to 26.21%, this information comes to them from the Internet.

It is equally worth highlighting that 58.25% of our respondents do not know what Universities of the Third Age are, as opposed to remaining 41.75%, who do.

For the majority of them, the main reason to participate in training activities is “Finding out about things and Getting new information” (66.02%), even though “Meeting People and improving social contact” is also a strong

reason (58.25%), together with “Being more active” (48.54%) and “Improving quality of life in retirement” (33.01%). Likewise, an outstanding proportion of 19.42% mention ‘Overcoming isolation’ as their main reason. According to 72.82% of interviewees, the possibility of receiving more information and a higher availability of formative activities would be a way to boost their level of participation and this is actually one of the measures that they suggest in their answers to the last item on the survey questionnaire.

By contrast, another 27.18% would not take part in such activities all the same, for reasons mainly associated with personal and health problems (32.14%), due to lack of suitable means of transport (35.71%) or distance from venues (35.71%). These factors linked to dependence, reduced (or lack of) mobility or difficulty to get to the place where the formative action develops, along with lack of spare time (10.71%) and Personal Commitments – e.g. taking care of relatives – (14.29%) explain why that high percentage of individuals do not (or would not) participate.

The social aspect of training (learning inside a group and in direct contact with the teacher) appears as essential for 96.12% of interviewees, with a prevailing role being played by aspects such as relationships with people, sharing experiences, being able to ask and interact and enjoying the pedagogy and knowledge of a good teacher, in addition to finding a good reason to leave home for many seniors who thus force themselves to take care of themselves (dressing up and looking good), going out, walking and spending time with other activity partners.

However, it is worth stressing that up to 45.63% of our respondents would be willing to use new technologies and the Internet – either on their own or in groups – to follow a training programme. This percentage includes a majority of people who, despite claiming not to be familiar with them or not to master them, would like to learn if someone helps them. Similarly, a small group highlights the advantages of this option in terms of convenience because you can learn from home and with flexible timetables, and they also point out that a huge number of possibilities for zero-cost learning are available on the Internet.

With regard to questions about the subjects or topics that respondents would like to focus on or develop, they cover a very wide spectrum, as specified in the answers to question B.8. They can be summarised in groups of subjects for: 1) Most answers stress the interest to learn new things, because they believe that it is very good and important to keep

acquiring knowledge and to know more and more; 2) Age and its relationship with the fast changes that take place; this is an important aspect to justify participation in training; 3) The usefulness of training for physical and emotional training; 4) The aims of “distraction, entertainment, desire to socialise and participate”; 5) Covering personal aspirations of personal achievement and development by means of an education that they did not receive while they were children or youngsters; 6) As a necessary step in the preparation for retirement; 7) the need to continue training themselves in their profession as part of a process to update the knowledge and to improve the self-esteem of active seniors; 8) Training to feel useful and help others.

Interviewees suggest launching personalised dissemination campaigns (lectures) which show them the goodness of these training actions and their practical side (with specific examples or cases); they ask for proximity and convenience so that they can take part in them (in their centres, near them, with flexible timetables); and with teachers, instructors or volunteers who are capable of satisfying the formative needs of seniors (pedagogy, patience, empathy) sometimes limited by physical and emotional issues or others related to culture or studies.

It finally deserves to be mentioned that our group of interviewees includes highly diverse realities when it comes to personal autonomy, cultural level, place of residence and various services available to them, and economic situation, as well as the motivation which encourages them to participate. This is consequently a very heterogeneous group that would require different responses and action plans suited to their demands and necessities.

CONCLUSIONS - Bratislava

The aim of the EduSenNet project is to formulate recommendations for the stimulation of the people over 50 to keep up learning and to take part in educational activities. The presented report is used as a basis for the innovation of the learning programmes for older persons who are not included in the learning process. The group of the respondents consisted of one third of the inhabitants from the residential home and half of them were from a small town and village. Therefore the educational level of the respondents was not very high and the survey shows 7.34% of the

respondents with primary education and only 39.45% who graduated from the university. The respondents from other partners' survey have a higher educational level. It appears from this, that positive opinions on and interest in learning in later life are expressed only in 73.4% and 26.6% of the respondents think that learning in later life is not important.

Therefore we appreciate it very much that one request for opening a study and forming the UTA group came from a group of seniors in the North of Slovakia in the town of Námestovo, where we carried out a research.

Immediately we made a new educational offer to this pilot group of 104 older people.

The 'Human and Health' study program was opened for this group in September 2015. We detected another interest in the residential home in Lamač (suburb of Bratislava) where we started learning activities for the residents on the premises of the home in February 2016.

This experience shows us that the research in the groups of seniors has an immediate impact on the older persons who have been interviewed. The outcomes of the project are directly visible and practically implemented into the life of the persons and put into practice. Since February 2017 we have offered new possibilities in residential home Lamač focusing on historical themes.

CONCLUSIONS – Brno

The survey was carried out in Brno and its neighborhood (South Moravian Region).

Important facts:

- Focus on older adults who have an interest in learning but need some guidance or assistance in joining U3A programs.
- The dominant group of the respondents comes from the city of Brno (85%).
- Gender distribution: male 45%, female 55%.
- Age distribution: 50 – 60 years 18%, 61 – 70 years 45%, 71 – 80 years 32%, 81+ years 5%.
- Greater part of the respondents (97%) claims not to have any difficulties in joining learning activities.

- The main reasons to participate in training activities are “finding out about things and getting new information” and “improving quality of life in retirement”. Overcoming an isolation as the reason is insignificant, because 59% of the respondents live with other family members in a flat or a house.
- The most respondents discovered various formative possibilities and obtained information about them directly from their friends, relatives, and colleagues.
- Answers to the question “Which other learning activities for the over 50s in your region are you familiar with?": IT-courses, foreign language courses, sports and dancing courses, health courses.
- Answers to the question “Which of these learning activities would be suitable for you?": IT-courses, foreign language courses, health courses, sports courses.
- It is important to stress, that the answers of both groups above are very similar.
- As for the type of education that respondents would prefer are, in the first place, lectures.
- The social aspect is very important for most of the respondents.

CONCLUSIONS - Groningen

With our target group in mind – older people with higher education whom we expect to experience some difficulties in attending educational activities - the following aspects of the collected information are noteworthy:

Financial, logistical and physical hindrances:

- The costs of educational activities is one of the major hindrances;
- The distance from home to course location is an issue for many respondents;
- One’s own health or the health of the partner forms a hindrance for taking part in educational activities.

Concerning new media:

- It is surprising that none of the respondents stated that he/she is not able to use a computer;
- A small number of the respondents stated that they have an aversion against working with a computer;

- A great number is open to the use of new media in support of education.

But a considerable number of the respondents appreciate social aspects of learning and contacts with co-students.

Concerning free time:

- Obligations in the family withhold a considerable number of the respondents from taking part in education;
- Education must compete with a multitude of other activities on offer;
- Many people over 50 want to keep up learning to cope with the fast development of the society;
- The awareness level of the Senioren Akademie could be higher, considering that about a quarter of the respondents are former students and know the institution per definition.

CONCLUSIONS - Seniorenkolleg TU Chemnitz

The selection of non-students was focused on the town of Chemnitz and the suburban and rural area in a 50 km radius (districts Zwickau and Mittelsachsen, Erzgebirgskreis).

The region of Chemnitz has, on average, the oldest population of Germany. Out of the 246,654 inhabitants (state 31.07.2016) 48.34% are older than 50 years. The distribution is: 13.70% in the age group of 50 to 59 years, 13.83% are aged 60 to 69 years, 13.14% are aged 70 to 79 years and 7.66% are older than 80 years. This demographic development is expected to continue. According to calculations Chemnitz could have the oldest urban population in Europe by 2025. As a result the city of Chemnitz and the Technische Universität Chemnitz have the special responsibility to offer and further develop educational programmes for elderly people. The experiences gained that way are to be at the disposal of other regions that deal with similar demographic development tendencies, where it is highly probable to expect a such a development.

The survey encompassed people of the age group over 50, whose access to educational offers is often limited. To reach as many people of this certain age group as possible, different institutions and organisations that are frequented by senior citizens, were contacted. This especially included

social stations, welfare companies, societies, socio-cultural centres as well as gathering places and civic centres for communication, that offer no or little educational opportunities of their own. Social stations provide care, meals and events for older citizens. Sadly we were not able to recruit seniors, mostly over the age of 80, for interviews there.

The geographical allocation of the 109 survey participants shows, that 22.9% live in urban areas with over 50,000 inhabitants (Chemnitz) and 43.1% in smaller towns with under 50,000 inhabitants. 30.3% of the older non-students are living in rural areas (villages or local communities with less than 10,000 inhabitants). 37.6% of the participants were male, while 62.4% were female. More than 60% of the survey population were between 65 and 80 years old and only one interviewee was younger than 50 years.

11.9% of the survey participants discontinued their education after the 4th grade and 22.0% successfully completed their secondary education. 2.8% attended grammar school and graduated with their A levels. A big amount of the elders attended a university of applied sciences (Fachhochschule) (31.2%) or has an academic degree (27.5%). 4.6% of the survey participants completed a different kind of education, like specialist training (Facharbeiterausbildung).

41.3% of the questioned elderly live by themselves or with a partner (45.0%) in an apartment or a house. 12.8% of the survey attendants permanently live with other family members, for example with their children or grandchildren. This results in the high share of singles in the Seniorenkolleg.

We added questions to the questionnaire that we had coordinated with our project partners, that are relevant for the specific development of the Seniorenkolleg at the TU Chemnitz. To facilitate answering the German translation of the questionnaire was written in an "easily understandable language". Scientific specialist terms were avoided in order to reduce the inhibition threshold when answering and to rule out faulty interpretations.

Additionally, the use of terms out of the English-speaking-world (e.g. U3A), that are not commonly known in the region, was relinquished. These terms were replaced by periphrases (like educational offers for elders at colleges and universities).

Subsequently some remarkable answers to learning:

The share of survey participants, that view learning in later life as important is, with 84.4%, very high. The participants state, that learning aids in

staying young and healthy. Others declare that learning has effects on their social lives as well, since they meet other people during lectures/courses and on excursions.

Selected interesting quotations: "Learning is important to me for being able to have a say in certain things and also to be able to be above the ageing majority, so that my offspring is proud of me." "I want to stay active. To reach understanding of the youth." "I like to take advice from the younger generation." "Learning is important for my international correspondence, travels (foreign language), computer usage."

The participants tendentiously prefer learning offers that take place in the morning or afternoon, because their mental power is at its highest around these times. The survey participants stated that in the evening they are often too tired to learn.

The following simplification measures of attendance at learning activities were additionally named by survey participants:

- less personal obligations, more free time
- better health

Answers, especially from rural regions:

- local offers, offers in the residence or residential district, more courses in close proximity
- good accessibility to the place of learning
- learning together with others, lift sharing to the place of event

Additional questions of the Seniorenkolleg

64.2% of the survey participants are members in a club, with sports clubs being especially popular (18.3%).

41.3% of the questioned people volunteer in their free time. The area of activity is widely spread and includes: civic associations, political parties or youth development. However, the number of survey participants who are not volunteering is, with 54.1%, relatively high.

Result: In comparison to survey participants that live in cities with more than 50,000 inhabitants, the number of those surveyed from rural areas (villages under 10,000 inhabitants) and small-towns up to 50,000 inhabitants, that volunteer or are members of clubs, is higher.

The majority of questioned elders (35.8%) prefer to be labelled as "retirees"(recipient of pension scheme) or "seniors" (31.2%). 7.3% of the

population report, that foreign appellations that reduce people to their age are being viewed as discriminatory. They prefer to be seen as people and to be called Miss/Misses / Mister.

Summary

We will use the results of the report to develop new educational programmes for elderly people and to motivate them to participate in learning activities, like the Seniorenkolleg of the TU Chemnitz.

In rural regions we are already preparing new workshops for the “Newcomers“ amongst the seniors, who are now starting to explore the field of learning in later life. Our goal is it to motivate them to participate in application oriented education. To achieve that we reach out to gathering places for elderly people. There we collectively watch a lecture of the Seniorenkolleg via livestream, which we moderate and discuss together with the seniors. We started out with presentations on culture (e.g. music, theatre) to pick the elders up at their interests. In the rural regions we used gatherings in churches, clubs and other meeting places as well as in the civic centers.

CONCLUSIONS – Magdeburg

The percentage related to male/female, age and level of education of the respondents is considerably equal to the participants all in all.

Reasons, preventing persons from taking part in educational activities are professional and personal duties, furthermore lack of free time.

It has been proven that first of all persons who already taken part in courses “Study over 50” contribute to encourage elderly people to join courses, to participate in educational activities.

Personal contacts are the major source of information about the offered program for new participants.

Lectures, seminars and excursions are the favorite activities

History, Natural Science, Political Science and scientific subjects are of particular interest.

The respondents are well informed about the learning facilities in their region. At the same time their learning activities are diverse. In the past a majority of the respondents attended courses at the adult evening classes (Volkshochschule), Urania or did other learning activities, such as adult education in rural areas, church educational institutes as well as various

foundations. Many of them cooperate with “Study over 50”. These include: Otto-von-Guericke-Company, registered association Emeritus, association Historico-Cultural Museum Magdeburg. The results confirm that it is very important to maintain such a cooperation, to draw potential participants’ attention to the offers of the university.

How do person of lower education (not being so interested in learning activities) get to know something about the university?

The results show, that the offers “Study about 50” first of all appeal to persons who have a higher education (a vast majority with an academic degree) and second persons, who are engaged in other activities, i. e. (members of associations or doing voluntary work). Most of the persons are well informed about the educational opportunities, had already taken part in some courses offered by “Study over 50” and attended courses of other educational institutions. Learning and education in general play a very important role, even referring to older age, mentioned by respondents. Persons, who are not interested in learning, are not affected by the offer. Educationally alienated people don’t relatively often participate in institutional qualification, also because of different social reasons and they have less participation chances. It’s about a whole heterogeneous group, assuming that for most people of this group, social and cultural reasons of an underprivileged environment are characteristic: social background, families with a low social status, low education, low professional qualification resulting in appropriate job, sometimes difficult professional and familiar conditions, living in discriminating regions.

The main lash of a university is research and education. Scientific qualification is as well of great importance. Classes, lectures, seminars dealing with professional and general higher qualification are offered. Forms are courses of studies, certificate courses, long term and short term further education courses.

The largest group involves: persons with a university degree of all subject areas, skilled workers and citizens, different age-groups interested in educational activities.

For persons who are not interested in educational learning activities or those who have a low qualification, the university doesn’t offer many courses, because it’s not the task of the university. It cannot be the task of a university.

It can be imaginable to develop an advice center (system) for this target group. The staff of the university can support such a center with regard to didactics and teaching methods and train instructors.

It is to mention that learning activities for these persons cannot be realized at a university, because a university has the essential task to teach scientific knowledge. This group will also not be taken into consideration of the program "Study over 50".

There are very big differences concerning education and social environment, it is also too difficult to arrange them an educational program to integrate. Educational and professional differences are too big within these participants' groups.

CONCLUSIONS - Uppsala

We note that 75% of the respondents are more than 71 years of age, which we should have in mind when comparing with seniors from other countries. Only 11% of them have any sort of health problem that will make it difficult for them to join learning activities. The majority of the respondents are old and healthy!

Most of the respondents (77%) are interested in learning in later life and they have knowledge about Universities of the third age.

The main reasons for taking part in learning activities are to get new knowledge (35%), and improved social contacts (24%) to get an improved quality of life. Most people say that they have no reason for not taking part in learning activities and many people mention lack of spare time as a reason for not taking part. 58% of the respondents mention that the social aspect is important.

Lectures and seminars / discussions are the most popular types of education. Half of the respondents are positive to new media.

Many respondents say that they need some sort of support for their inner motivation to join learning activities in later life.

QUESTIONNAIRE

used for the EduSenNet survey "HELPING THE OVER 50's" focusing on older people

EduSenNet is a European funded project designed for people over 50 years of age. Researchers from 6 different European countries will be working together to find the best ways of helping older people fulfil their learning needs through the later years of their working lives and in retirement. The project will focus on how later life can be enriched through learning activities of all kinds. Many of the project workers are themselves older volunteers, learners over 50 who have benefitted from and are experienced in such activities.

We are seeking those older people who have an interest in learning but need guidance or assistance to join educational programmes. The attached questionnaire is designed to provide us the basic information for working out appropriate measures. You will see that no names are required so you can be certain that your information will only be used as part of the general findings of this research.

We would be very grateful if you could complete this questionnaire which we hope will only take a few minutes of your time.

Thank you very much.

The questionnaire is in 2 parts, **A** and **B**.

Part A is about **you** and Part B is about **you and learning**.

Please tick the item(s) most appropriate to you

A.1 The country in which you live

- a/ Czech Republic
- b/ Germany
- c/ Netherlands
- d/ Slovakia
- e/ Spain
- f/ Sweden

A.2 Your Gender

- a/ Male
- b/ Female

A.3 Your age

- a/ 50 -60
- b/ 61 -70
- c/ 71 -80
- d/ 81+

A.4 Education (please tick as appropriate):

- a) Primary
- b) Secondary
- c) University
- d) Other

A.5 Where do you live (please tick as appropriate):

- a/ In a town or city
- b/ In a village / country

A.6 Housing (please tick as appropriate):

- a/ Alone in your own apartment or house
- b/ With members of your family in an apartment or house
- c/ In a residential home
- d/ Other forms of housing.....

A.7. Do you have a physical handicap or health problem that makes it difficult for you to join learning events?

- a/ Yes
- b/ No

B. LEARNING

B.1 Do you think learning in later life is important and are you interested in taking part in learning activities

- a/ Yes
- b/ No

Please describe the reason why yes/no

B.2 How do you find out about learning possibilities? / Where can you find out about learning possibilities?

- a) friends, family, colleagues
- b) advertising
- c) internet
- d) newspaper
- e) TV/ radio
- f) other (please describe).....
- g) I do not know

B.3 Do you know any University of the Third Age?

- a) Yes
- b) No

B.4 Which other learning activities for the over 50s in your region are you familiar with?

.....

B.5 Which of these learning activities would be suitable for you?

.....

B.6 Which of the following do you think are good reasons for taking part in learning activities?

- a) finding out about things / getting new information
- b) meeting people and improving social contact
- c) overcoming isolation
- d) being more active
- e) improving the quality of life in retirement
- f) other (please specify).....

B.7 Would more information and a wider range of learning activities persuade you to take part?

- a) Yes
- b) No

B.8 If yes, which subjects would interest you?

(The attached list of subjects of current UTA courses can be used as a guide, but you are free to write down other subjects)

B.9 If no, what would prevent you from taking part? (Max. 3)

- a) personal health problems
- b) partner's health problems
- c) lack of spare time
- d) personal commitments (e.g. Caring for family members)
- e) distance from venue
- f) lack of suitable travel facilities
- g) financial problems
- h) not enough quality teachers
- i) other.....

B.10 Which type of education would you prefer?

- a) lectures
- b) seminars
- c) excursions
- d) discussions
- e) exercises, training
- f) other (please specify).....

B.11

Is the social aspect of learning important for you (learning in a group in direct contact with the lecturer)?

- a/ Yes
- b/ No

The reason why yes or no?

B.12

Would you like to use new media for learning either at home or in a group (e.g. courses on cd, live transmissions of lectures via internet)?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) I don't know

The reason why yes or no?

B.13

What sort of measures comes to your mind that would make it easier for you to take part in learning?

.....

B.14

If you are not involved in educational activities, what other activities and recreational activities do you practice?

- a) reading books
- b) gardening
- c) Babysitting
- d) singing, dancing, musical activities, sport activities
- e) art activities, folk art, handiwork
- f) Volunteering
- g) Traveling
- h) other (please specify)

7. FEASIBILITY STUDY OF THE PROJECT EduSenNet Survey among the older students

7.1. Universidad Permanente – Universidad de Alicante HELPING OVER-50s Survey among students

INTRODUCTION

The EduSenNet project is designed to gather and share information, to make a wider and improved use of all these rich experiences, building upon them, analysing and assessing their value and impact on seniors, disseminating research evidence and, of course, creating a network to do all this.

During this first stage, we have been working with a survey questionnaire for senior students designed to provide and obtain the basic information that will make it possible to plan the most suitable measures and proposals to ensure that many other people can benefit from these training programmes and actions oriented to seniors, regardless of their background, their socio-cultural status or their level of autonomy and mobility.

The period comprised the months of April and May of 2015. The survey was conducted online with the Lime Survey tool and after a previous information campaign that promoted the objectives of this project.

The aforesaid questionnaire asks interviewees about their needs, fears, formative experiences and opinions regarding the different types of training and how to become involved in them. This survey carried out by each one of the network partners allowed us to achieve interesting outcomes as well as to prepare the national report that we are now presenting from the Permanent University of the University of Alicante.

STUDY

Our attention focuses on those older adults enrolled in our educational programme – Permanent University of the University of Alicante. The attached questionnaire is designed to supply essential information so that we can devise appropriate measures.

The survey is divided into the following areas of analysis: two separate sections, the first one referring to socio-demographic aspects as tools used to define our interviewees' profiles (Place of Living, Age; Gender; Level of education; and Activities); and a second one related to the educational programme (how did they get in contact with the UPUA, opinion about the educational activities, motivations for the educational activities, interests, plans for the future regarding their education and finally preferences (schedule, duration and location).

Seniors to which the EduSenNet surveys for UPUA students are addressed

The surveys are addressed to any resident of the Alicante province above 50 years of age who aspires socio-cultural improvement and without being required any previous qualifications.

All the answers and conclusions supplied by these groups of interviewees and collected in this report attempt to offer a general overview of the situation.

BASIC SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC DATA - INTERVIEWEES' PROFILE

Gender: *Figure 1: Participants according to gender (in percentage)*

The total number of surveys completed in Spain **amounted to 357.**

50.98% of them being from women and the remaining 49.02% from men.

Age: *Table 1: Participants according to age groups (in percentage)*

	50 – 60	61 – 70	71 - 80	81 and older
Students	21.85%	56.58%	19.89%	1.68%

It is worth highlighting the significant proportion of over-70s involved in the survey (21.57% of respondents) which already suggests a considerable level of interest in our study object.

Educational level: Table 2: Respondent's educational level (in percentage)

2.80%	30.81%	57.42%	8.96%
Primary	Secondary	University	Other

As for level of education, those who have finished a university degree stands out in first place (accounting for 57.42% of the sample), followed by individuals with a secondary school level (30.81%). A group representing up to 8.96% of respondents claim to have completed a different level - an answer which tends to be related to professional studies or medium - level vocational training certifications of a technical nature. Only 2.80 of the respondents have finished the primary school.

Area of residence: Table 3: Respondents' area of residence

Town	82.91%	Village	17.09%
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With regard to the area of residence, 82.91% of respondents have their homes in relatively large cities or towns of more than 100,000 inhabitants, whereas 17.09% live in smaller towns or villages/rural areas (with population figures ranging between 10,001 and 100,000 inhabitants).

Activities: Figure 2: Activities

With regard to the activities, most of the respondents devote their free time to hobbies 35.57%, household activities 32.49% and other activities 28.85%. A reduced group is still working. It is worth highlighting the time devoted to altruistic activities such as volunteering 11.48% or care of family and grandchildren.

LEARNING

Which of the following statements fits best your digital activities?

Figure 3: Statements that fit best with digital activities

According to the obtained results, practically all of the respondents have a computer. A high percentage also have a smartphone, whereas tablet is the technological resource that 61.34% of the interviewees have.

In order to carry out the digital activities, the main tool used by the interviewees is the computer (50.70%), followed by the smartphone and the tablet at the same level.

A reduced percentage of the interviewees, lower than 11%, need help to carry out the activities with digital resources, whereas more than 54% are able to use a computer and smartphone without help.

How did you get in contact with the Permanent University?

The students' first contact with the UPUA was through friends and relatives (78.71%) who have conveyed the benefits of learning at the institution. Internet also has an important role as the first contact source with the UPUA, accounting for more than 12.04% of the answers.

Figure 4: Means of contact with the UPUA

What are in your opinion the main motivations for educational activities? *Figure 5: Main motivations for educational activities*

As for the main motivations to undertake educational activities, the one that stands out the most is “self-development”, accounting for 71.99% of the answers. Secondly, it is worth mentioning “productive ways to spend time” (37.82%), followed by “information on several topics” (31.37%) and “the acquisition of practical skills” (30.81%). Equally important, a group of students has been involved in the training activities to meet new people with similar interests (22.41%).

When did you attend your first educational activities at the Permanent University? *Figure 6: (courses, trips, seminars, discussions, workshops)*

As for the beginning of the activity in the UPUA, most of the respondents started to take part between two and five years ago. It is worth highlighting that there are people still interested in the academic activities of the institution even though they undertook training activities more than ten or fifteen years ago.

Give your reaction to the following statement: "The attended educational activities have been up to my expectations"

More than 80% of the respondents think that the training activities of the UPUA they have attended live up to their expectations. Only 1.12% does not agree.

Figure 7: The attended educational activities have been up to the students' expectations

If you didn't attend educational activities at UPUA, can you state why?

The main reasons why the students have not attended the training activities sometime are personal circumstances, unsuitable schedule, time constraints as well as other reasons not mentioned.

Figure 8: Main reasons why the students have not attended the training activities at UPUA

Are you planning to attend educational activities at the Permanent University during the following year?

It is worthy of note the very high percentage of respondents (89.64%) that want to keep being enrolled next year in the training activities of the UPUA. Only 2.24% will not continue to be enrolled in the UPUA and 8.12% still do not know.

Figure 9: Interest in being enrolled next year in the training activities of the UPUA

Which of the following subjects interests you the most?

As for the subjects of interest, Humanities stands out with 73.39% of the respondents, followed by Computer Science, Image and Sound with 43.68%.

Figure 10: Subjects of interest

Which period do you prefer to attend a course?

Figure 11: Period of preference

Are you interested in attending courses in the evening or during the weekend?

Figure 12: Preference in the weekdays

Practically all the interviewees (93.84%) prefer attending classes during the week and only 3.92% would be interested in some kind of training at the weekends.

What is your preferred length for a course/session?

Figure 13: Preference for course length

Figure 14: Preference for session length

Which course location do you prefer?

Figure 15: Preference in the course location

In which sequence of importance would you place the following options for the choice of a course? (from 1 as most important to 10 as less important)

With regard to the ranking of importance when choosing subjects, the subject itself takes the first place, which shows that the topic is the main motive when choosing subjects. Secondly, the teaching staff takes almost 30%, as well as if known people are also taking the subject. This last fact shows that the UPUA activities are an integration and social cohesion mechanism.

Figure 16: Ranking of importance when choosing a course

Figure 17: Courses attended since the first enrollment

Figure 18: Courses attended per year at UPUA

QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT: NEW TRENDS

Once the survey and the quantitative analysis have finished, and based on analysing the evolution of the Senior Diploma programme during its 17 years of existence, we can suggest by way of conclusion that certain changes and new trends are emerging within the profile of students and their needs and demands.

The percentage of participation of men and women is increasingly put on a level each year. A decrease has thus been experienced in the gender difference between participants in the UPUA programme –which was mostly female in its early years.

There is a growing presence of the age group comprised between 50 and 60 years and that of over-80s, even though the majority group continues to be the one formed by 61-to-70-year-olds. A significant change has taken place in the profile of students, who have a better and better educational level. Up to 75% of the students who access the programme have completed three-year or five-year university degrees.

A remarkable transformation has also been operated in the selection of contents/subjects that students want to develop. Humanities, which had traditionally been by far the most often followed area of knowledge among older adult students, has reduced its number of enrolled students during the last few years in favour of subjects belonging to the areas of Health and Social Action, Experimental Sciences, Social and Legal Sciences, and ICTs.

Students demand subjects which combine theoretical contents with others of a practical nature that can be easily applied to everyday life. The number of older adult students interested in blended and online training is increasing. More and more older adult students are willing to become involved in research as well as in exchanges between study programmes and centres for seniors, both nationally and internationally.

There is a growing interest in the development of intergenerational training activities. A considerable number of senior students participate to an increasingly great extent in collaborative learning schemes, peer-to-peer training and voluntary service initiatives, within the framework of the UPUA Senior Diploma Programme.

7.2. Bratislava, Comenius University, UTA Survey among the older students

The University of the Third Age (UTA) under the auspices of Comenius University was established in 1990 as the first institution of this kind in the Slovak Republic. UTA is located at the Centre for Continuing Education of Comenius University, as one of the centre's department. UTA organizes courses mainly for retired people, for medically retired (physically handicapped) and for people before retirement generally for people over 50. It offers the students a 3year study programmes in about 39 study branches in 4 cities (Bratislava, Nitra, Martin and in Námestovo (central and North of Slovakia).

The study plan of each year provides for 14 three-hour lectures to be presented each fortnight. During the first year the students are offered basic lectures from each of the offered disciplines. Their second and third year is devoted to the study of optional disciplines and students enrol in the study of specialised branches. The interest in this form of study constantly increases. Yearly almost 2,000 elderly students enrol in 68 study groups. After completing their study, students are ceremonially given certificates. The pedagogical process at the UTA is complemented by other educational and social forms. Along with lectures and seminars, we organise excursions, panel discussions, visits to other universities, informal meetings and conceptualised trips. Topics, which are the same or similar to those in undergraduate courses, are given by university lecturers either from our faculties or from partner ones. There are about 300 lecturers at our UTA altogether.

In our survey we have contacted some of our students from many different groups and places of learning, group totaled **329 respondents**. From them 90% of respondents have their place of living in the town and only 10% in the village. Along with Bratislava (86%), there are from other regions 14% (from Trenčín, Trnava, Senec -South-west of Slovakia and in the central part of Slovakia from Žilina and Banská Bystrica).

UTA has yearly about 89% of female and 11% of male registered in its learning activities. The survey includes fewer men (9%) and more women (91%) than are usual in our study programmes. The scale of the respondent's age includes 11% of those at ages 50-60; 65% of the

respondents are at age 61-70; 22% of the respondents at age 71-80 and the rest of respondents 2% are the respondents over 80.

The elderly who want to study at UTA of Comenius University have to graduate from the secondary school and be over 50. Therefore we have not included in our survey the respondents with the primary educational level. Group of the respondents with university academic level consists of 11% which shows high interest of the retired experts in continuing education. The respondents with secondary education are in 39% and the respondents with level of tertiary education and university graduates are in 50%. This scale corresponds with the general educational scale of the UTA students. The concrete opinions, wishes, interests and experience of the respondents from Comenius University are described in the results which follow.

Our UTA is very well known in the public and in society. Since we started in 1990 we have now second generation of the students who already have knowledge about UTA from their friends and relatives (55%). Other students have information from the Internet advertisements in 14% and from the websites in 13%. What is for us important to know, that advertisements have 20% of the success.

Figure 1: How did you get into contact with UTA?

In the questions given to the contacted students we focused on many subjects. Senior students have a large scale of interests. Division of their activities in spare time is shown in the figure 2.

Figure 2: Interests in spare time activities

UTA yearly offers PC courses for 100 students to improve digital literacy of the elderly. There is also possibility to enrol in the subject of the financial learning where are the computers regularly used during the lectures. We found out, that from 329 respondents there are 128 (41%) who have a computer and use it regularly for email and occasional browsing on the internet. Other 106 respondents (34%) answered “I have a computer, a tablet and a smartphone and can work with all three of them unassisted”. The 23 group of students (7%) who have a computer, a tablet and a smartphone need regularly assistance. We can say that we have 82% of those who use the technical equipment and modern ICT technologies daily or regularly. The rest of our respondents 50 (16%) are those who have normal mobile phone and do not use a tablet or those 4 (1%) who seldom use a computer and do not have a mobile phone nor a tablet. In our age scale we can see, that 24% of the respondents are over 71, which also can influence the results described below and 17% of the respondents who need to improve their digital literacy. Question B3. focused on the motivation for study at UTA.

Figure 3: Motivation for educational activities

The results show us changing of the senior's motivation. In the past (15 years ago) there was on the top the interest to get knowledge. Now are the interests more practical shown in the categories of personal development and practical skills. From the group of respondents there are many of them who attend UTA for more than 10 years (13%) and other 24% attend our courses for more than 5 years. It means that after graduation in one course they enrol in new study subjects and do study circles again. We can see high satisfaction with the educational process, activities and the level of teaching at our UTA. We regularly update the study offer according to the interests of the elderly students and the teaching level is managed on a high level by the lecturers from the faculties of Comenius University and the specialists from the scientific university centres. All students included in the survey agreed with the statement: *"The attended educational activities have been up to my expectations"*. (Q B7., Q.B8.)

The situation described above brought us to the interest to know how many courses the respondents have attended since they started their study at our university. In our survey we contacted from 322 respondents (100%) 66% of them (212) who attend first or second study subject. The rest of 110 respondents (34%) are those who attend third or have attended several subjects (Details in the figure 4)

Figure 4: How many courses have you attended so far?

For the managers and organisers of the study programmes it is very important to know if the students or graduates have further interests to attend study and offered activities in a coming year or in future. On the other hand it is very useful to know the reason why the students did not attend educational activities.

Figure 5 : When you did not attend educational activities, can you state why? (tick max. 2)

There are many older students at Comenius University who frequently enrol in new study subject after finishing the previous one. Therefore we could see many students who attended more than one study subject and are planning to continue in the next year. There are 303 respondents (95%), who already decided to continue, other 13 (4%) are not definitely decided and only 1% (4 respondents) do not have interest to continue. The reasons not to attend our UTA are as follows: lack of time, lack of money, health reasons and personal circumstances. The figures show that the interest in the study is permanent and many of contacted students attend our studies regularly and periodically. When we asked our respondents how many courses they attended per year or in this study year, we found out that in our group there are 221 (68%) of those who enrolled in and study one subject, two subjects are attended by 59 students (18%) and the rest of them 44 (14%) attend three or more than three subjects.

Figure 6: Which of the following subjects interests you most? (tick max.3)

Comenius University in Bratislava has 13 faculties and 12 of them are involved in the study programmes for UTA. Besides we have half of the students (around 1,000) who are enrolled at the Faculty of Arts. Therefore we can see in this survey 58% of the respondents interested in the study subjects belonging to this faculty. Other opinions correspond with the subjects at the Faculty of Medicine, Faculty of Law, Faculty of

Natural sciences or Faculty of Theology. We noticed the transformation in the study subjects concerning PC courses (15 years ago about 150, now fewer students – only 60 students yearly enrol in the PC courses).

Other questions in our survey focused on the period of the day, days in the week devoted to learning, length of the courses. Location of the educational activities as well as the general conditions for study and requirements of the students.

In further questions we asked our students (329 respondents) which period they preferred to attend a course and if they were interested in attending courses in the evenings or during the weekend.

Respondents	Before noon	Afternoons	Anytime	Do not know	No answer
329	155 (47%)	44 (13%)	6 (1.8%)	64 (19%)	60 (19%)

Table 1: Which period do you prefer to attend a course

Respondents	Only weekdays	Evenings and weekends	Evening	Weekend	Do not know
329	290 (88%)	6 (1.8%)	8 (2.5%)	12 (3.7%)	13 (4%)

Table 2: Are you interested in attending courses in the evenings or during weekends.

The learning activities as lectures and seminars are usually organised during the work days. Seniors don't like to participate in the activities in the evenings. They prefer daily hours because they are mostly already retired. We have only 5% of the students who are still at a professional age (age group 50 – 60). During weekends we usually organise study excursions, if not on workdays.

The question B.14 focused on the opinion about the length for a course.

Respondents	Less than 5 lectures	5-8 lectures	More than 8 lectures	No preference	Planned length suits me	No answer
329	4 (1%)	28 (8.5%)	40 (12%)	39 (12%)	210 (64%)	8 (2.5%)

Table 3: What is your preferred length for a course?

The study programme consists of 14 lectures in one academic year. The opinions of the respondents show us that the system of study suits them. Therefore the satisfaction of the respondents shown in Q B.7 and B.8 is very high.

Last questions of our survey focused on the course location and the opinions of the respondents for the choice of course concerning the most important conditions and their preferences for their personal decision. 24% of the respondents have preference in the venue of the study courses. Therefore all 39 study subjects are organised in the city centre.

Figure 7: Which course location has your preferences?

In the figure 8, we can see that the highest occurrence of responses in each option is considered relevant value. We can see that the subject is most important category for the students (T: 318 respondents). On the second position are the requests on the lecturers which means that seniors prefer high quality of the education.

Qualitative assessment: New trends and experience after 20 years show us the increase of gender difference (from 78% to 91% of women); students come with better educational level when enrol in courses of University of the Third Age (change from 1/5 to 1/2 of university graduates). It also influences the motivation of the students for study at UTA. We mentioned already in the part about motivation in study, that the motivation and interests of the elderly are also changing according to the changes in society and life needs. We can say conclusion, that seniors and the older students, especially, are more good at specifying their

needs, have higher expectations, educational needs with higher personal involvement and investment.

Figure 8 : In which sequence of importance would you place the following options for the choice of a course?

7.3. Brno Survey among the older students

Brno University of Technology - University of the Third Age

Brno is the second largest city in the Czech Republic and it is known as a center of science, research and innovations. With more than 20% of its population being students of six public universities, Brno is often dubbed "a city with student spirit". Its citizens as well as visitors are offered numerous cultural, sports and leisure activities. Established in 1899, Brno University of Technology (BUT) is the city's oldest university. Today it offers high-quality studies in engineering, scientific, economic and artistic fields. With its 24 thousand students and 8 faculties, BUT is the nation's largest technical university. Focusing on science and research, the university now has five of its own research centers being engaged in two centers of excellence. In recent years, BUT has been among the world's best universities according to QS Quacquarelli Symonds Limited, a

prestigious international ranking. As an EU member, Brno University of Technology was the country's second university in to receive both ECTS Label and Diploma Supplement certificate. Popular University of the Third Age programmes and courses are aimed at active seniors who are interested in fields ranging from technology to humanities to fine arts. In 2016 the University of the Third Age surveyed seniors as part of the **EduSenNet project**. There were **434 seniors** who responded to the survey. All seniors were from the Czech Republic. Presented in this report are highlights of the results from seniors' responses.

Key Findings and Highlights

Place of living: 92 % town, 8 % village

Region: 84 % Brno, 15 % South-Moravian Region, 1 % other.

Gender: 30 % male, 70 % female.

Age:

Age	50-60	61-70	71-80	80+	Total
%	7%	42%	49%	2%	434 = 100%

Educational level:

- Secondary 48 %
- University 38 %
- Ph.D. or higher 11 %
- Other 4 %

In the question focusing on **the activities of respondents in their spare time** we found out that seniors' students are active in many fields of their interests, which shows the following *Figure 1: Activities in spare time*

In our research we also focused on the Motivation of the elderly student at BUT. Our students enroll at the University of the Third Age because further development of themselves. It is meaningfully dominated in front of other categories as they are listed (to fulfil own free time useful, to obtain background information on current topics, to learn practical skills). It is important to know that 1/4 of the respondents have interest to meet other people with similar interests.

Figure 2: Motivation for educational activities

Figure 3: When you didn't attend educational activities, can you state why?

In the Figure 3 we can see that our respondents are very active and their biggest problem and personal reason not to attend educational activities is lack of time, when this category was chosen by 1/3 of the respondents. Other category “personal circumstances” was chosen by 1/4 of contacted elderly students of BUT.

The interest of the elderly students in the study subjects is clearly visible in the Figure 4, when the interests are oriented mainly to the Information and communication technologies. Concerning the main profile of the Brno University of Technologies it is understandable.

Figure 4: Which of the following subjects interests you most?

The academic year is divided into two semesters. Each semester consists of 12 weeks of classes. Duration of class is usually 90 minutes. The opinions of the respondents in Figure 5 show that the system of study suits them. Figure 5: What is your preferred length for a course?

The Figure 6 shows the priorities of the respondents in the subject of study prior to the day and the hours in the schedule of the courses as well as the personal engagement of the UTA lecturers.

Figure 6: In which sequence of importance would you place the following options for the choice of a course?

Conclusion

Our survey indicates what kinds of courses, instruction techniques and time of day work best for seniors. Lifelong learning is important for keeping the mind and memory working. Ongoing education and learning activities can compensate for age-related problems encourage seniors to develop and maintain social connections, improve their self-confidence and quality of live, and prevent social isolation. Computer use among older adults is soaring. Seniors at the Brno University of Technology actively want to learn about technology, mostly so they can keep up with their grandchildren and maintain contact with distant relatives.

7.4. Groningen

Comparison of surveys of the Senioren Academie Groningen-Friesland-Drenthe among students and non-students

- **Student satisfaction survey Groningen, May 2015, hereafter called “students”**
1241 respondents
- **Learning at later age, Desires and motivation of people over 50, October/November 2015, hereafter called “non-students”**
135 respondents

In the beginning of 2015 the Senioren Academie Groningen-Friesland-Drenthe conducted a survey among its senior students to investigate their satisfaction with the courses and to get a picture of their special interests and motivations.

In October/November 2015 the project workgroup for EduSenNet handed out its questionnaire to people over 50 who hadn't attended courses of the Senioren Academie during the previous four years, to investigate their needs, requirements, experiences, opinions and handicaps with respect to the various forms of learning.

When comparing the results of the two surveys one has to take into account that the questions and options for answering were not all identical.

The complete results of the two surveys can be found in <http://edusennet.efos-europa.eu/results/results-groningen/>.

1. Characteristics of the respondents

Gender

	Students	Non-students
Men	45%	42%
Women	55%	58%

The survey among non-students reached slightly more women.

Age

	51 – 60	61 – 70	71 – 80	81 and older
Students	25%	61%	13%	1%
Non-students	11%	44%	35%	10%

In both surveys the biggest group is in the range 61-70 years but the percentage of respondents above 70 is higher for non-students than for students.

Highest level of education

	Primary vocational education	Secondary (vocational) education	Higher professional and Academic education	Others
Students	4%	10%	85%	1%
Non-students	1%	16%	74%	9%

In both surveys a predominant part of the respondents had a higher professional or academic education. The level of education was slightly wider spread for non-students than for students.

2. Geographical distribution

In which province do you live?

	Groningen	Friesland	Drenthe	Others
Students	38%	13%	26%	23%
Non-students	12%	58%	29%	1%

Compared to the Students survey, Friesland is over-represented in the survey among non-students. This reflects the composition of the EduSenNet workgroup, the majority of its members living in Friesland .

Place of residence

	Town with course location	Other town	Countryside
Students	45%	12%	43%
Non-students	38%	11%	51%

Course locations of the Senioren Academie are: Groningen (200.216 inhabitants), Leeuwarden (107.856 inh.), Hoogeveen (54.665 inh.) en Emmen (107.687 inh.).

● Course locations of the Senioren Academie

3. Income

How does your income relate to the median income?

The median income is € 35.500 a year. (approximately € 2.025 net a month)

	Less than half median	Half median to median	Median to 2 times median	Above 2 times median	No answer
Students	5%	24%	47%	13%	11%

The non-students were not asked about their income.

4. What are your main reasons for attending a course?

Order of importance (1= high, 4 = low)

	Students	Non-students
1	To gain knowledge and insight To continue to develop myself	Finding out about things / getting new information
2	Because I like to learn new things To obtain background on current topics	Improving the quality of life in retirement
3	To fill my free time in a useful/interesting way To meet other people with similar interests To develop practical skills	Being more active
4	To delve in the meaning of life	Meeting people and improving social contacts

There are no remarkable differences between the motivation of students and non-students.

5. Reasons for not attending courses

Order of importance (1=high, 8=low)

	Students	Non-students
1	The point in time of the courses does not fit me	Too expensive
2	Lack of time	Lack of time
3	Distance to the course location	Distance to course location
4	I have only just become aware of the Senioren Academie, but I am soon going to follow my first course	Personal health problems
5	No interesting topics Health problems (personal or partner's)	Personal commitments (e.g. caring for family members)
6	Too expensive	Health problem of partner No adequate transportation
7	Personal circumstances (other than health)	Not enough quality teachers
8	The courses that seemed interesting were too long for me	

Both students and non-students have some common obstacles for attending courses:

- the costs of the courses
- lack of time
- the distance to the course location
- health problems

Note

Chapters 4 and 5 don't give a clear indication of why students found the way to the courses and non-students didn't, except for the costs that play a bigger role for non-students than for students.

6. Promotion

Students: How did you first get into contact with the Senioren Academie?

Non-students: How and where do you find out about learning possibilities?

	Do not know	50+ fair or education market	Advert. in door-to-door magazine	Course brochure	Internet	News paper	Family, friends, acquaintances
Students	14%	0%	0%	20%	15%	6%	45%
Non-students	2%	1%	6%	15%	30%	19%	27%

- The course brochure is an important promotion instrument. But mouth-to-mouth promotion plays a dominant part. To a slightly lesser extent the respondents get their information from internet, newspapers and door-to-door magazines.
- Non-students mention a broader range of information channels.

Note

1. From both surveys we can conclude that mouth-to mouth promotion is most effective.
2. Though non-students indicate that they are aware of the Senioren Academie and use a broad range of information they don't find their way to the Senioren Academie.

7. Besides studying, what are your most important (free time) activities?

Order of importance (1=high, 9=low)

	Students	Non-students
1	Hobbies	Reading
2	Voluntary work	Voluntary work
3	Household	Gardening
4	Care for (grand)children	Travelling
5	Part-time work	Sports
6	Family care	Art activities, painting
7	Education from another organisation	Singing, dancing, musical activities
8	Full-time work	Care for (grand)children

Older people are more active than in the past.

- We note that 86% of the students are younger than 70 years. A number of them are still working part-time or full-time and attend other courses.
- The majority of the surveyed non-students is older than 70 and live in villages. A national survey (MKB: facts about seniors, 2015) shows that older people in the countryside like gardening, travelling by caravan, sports and have a broad interest in cultural topics. They are socially involved and spend much time reading books. This corresponds quite well with our survey.

8. Which of the following subjects are you most interested in?

Order of importance (1=high, 10=low)

	Students	Non-students
1	History and archaeology	History
2	Philosophy	Art history, architecture, photography
3	Art history	Philosophy
3	Human sciences (psychology, sociology, anthropology)	Language and literature
4	Linguistics and literature	General/multidisciplinary Religious studies Music and theatre Human sciences (psychology, sociology, anthropology)

5	Music (history) Architecture Biology, nature and environment	Computer
6	Religious studies	Medicine Natural sciences
7	Mathematics and natural sciences, technology	Physical and social geography
8	Medicine	Economy
9	Economy	
10	Law	

There are no major differences between the areas of interest of students and non-students.

9. Customer satisfaction

The students were then asked whether they had attended courses during a longer time. These questions don't apply to non-students.

When did you attend your first course?

Year	%
In 2005 or earlier	29
In 2006	5
In 2007	4
In 2008	5
In 2009	4
In 2010	6
In 2011	7
In 2012	7
In 2013	12
In 2014	12
In 2015	5
I have not yet attended a course	4

How many courses have you attended since?

Number	%
1	19
2	11
3	10
4	7
5	8
6	7
7	4
8	4
9	2
10	4
More than 10	15
More than 20	6
More than 30	2

Note

- The Senioren Academie has a stable group of loyal students. Nearly 29% has participated for 10 years and more. Of this group 15% has attended at least one course every year.
- About 11 to 12% of the students stop after 2 or 3 years.

How many courses do you attend per year?

Number	%
Mostly one per year	55
Mostly two per year	36
Mostly three per year	7
Mostly four per year	2

Then the students were asked about their satisfaction with the Senioren Academie.

Statement: The course I attended met my expectations

Option	%
Totally agree	28
Agree	48
In some areas I do agree, in others I do not	23
Do not agree	1
Totally do not agree	1

The courses meet the expectations of the students. Other questions:

Are you planning to attend courses at the Senioren Academie in the coming year?

Option	%
Yes, I am planning to attend one or more course(s) within one year,	88
No, not the coming year. Probably next year.	11
No I am not planning to ever attend a course at the Senioren Academie	1

In which period would you prefer to follow a course?

Option	%
September - December	63
January - April	54
May - June	6
July - August	5

We can conclude that the students are satisfied with the Senioren Academie.

As a rule, satisfied students stay longer with an institution, an important fact for the management: ¹⁾

1. Acquisition of new students is more difficult/expensive than to hold existing students.
2. Services to existing students get easier/cheaper the longer they stay
3. The longer they stay the more courses the students attend.
4. Satisfied students generate an extra benefit with their mouth-to-mouth promotion to new potential students.

10. Digital developments

Our society develops in an exponential manner. Digitization has a big influence on almost every facet of it. Decrease in editions of newspapers and books, lending numbers at libraries and sales at shops are a clear

¹ Utpal M. Dholakia & Vicky Morwitz, How surveys influence customers, Harvard Business Review, 2002

indication. Those who don't adapt in time are running behind. That's why businesses and government concentrate increasingly on digital services. Is the Senioren Academie following this trend?

The non-students were asked:

Would you want to use new media for learning either at home or in a group?	Yes (60%)	No (40%)
Is the social aspect of learning important for you? (learning in a group in direct contact with the lecturer)	Yes (71%)	No (29%)

The non-students are interested in the digital developments but the social aspects of learning are very important for them. Learning in solitude at home is not attractive.

The students were asked whether they agreed with the following statements:

Statement	Agreement
I have a computer, tablet or smartphone and I can operate all three independently	41
I have a computer with internet and use it regularly (independently) for e-mail and I search on the internet. I have a normal (mobile) phone and use a tablet.	40
I use a computer, tablet and smartphone, but I often need help	9
I rarely use a computer, I have a normal (mobile) phone and no tablet	1
Others	9

Clearly, an increasing number of older people gets acquainted to digital devices.

11. Finally

The two surveys could not give a clear picture of why the non-students do not find their way to the Senioren Academie. So the EduSenNet workgroup attempted to get additional insight through discussions with two 'focus groups' (a selection of respondents of the non-student survey whose answers indicated that they had interesting ideas about this subject).

7.5. Chemnitz

Survey among participants of the Seniors College at TU Chemnitz

Part A: PERSONAL DATA

A.1 Region of living

All of the 162 survey participants (students) live in Germany, mostly in the city of Chemnitz. The others come from the surrounding administrative districts like the district Erzgebirge (10.5%), district Mittelsachsen (9.9%), district Zwickau (4.9%) and the town Wittenberg in the federal state of Saxony Anhalt.

A.2 Place of living

The geographical distribution of the respondents shows, that 73.0% live in a town and 16.0% live in a village. 11.0% did not answer.

A.3 Gender

There were 40.7% female and 56.2% male respondents. 3.1% did not respond. The high percentage of men is attributable to the fact, that many of the male attendees have completed technical studies – especially at the TU Chemnitz - and therefore have a close relation to the educational institute. The equal rate of men and women was also achieved through the choice of men and women specific topics of the lectures.

A.4 Age

The age distribution among the respondents: 43.8% of the population is between 61 and 70 years old, 51.2% between 71 and 80 years, 3.1% of the respondents are older than 81 years. Only one respondent is between 50 and 60 years old. 1.2%: no response.

A.5 Educational level

As the highest level of education only 1.2% of the participants finished after primary school and 5.6% after secondary school. 1.2% have their A levels. 8.6% of the participants have a vocational and 31.5% a professional degree (3 years). Most of the respondents (51.9%) of the Seniorenkolleg have a university degree (5 years of study).

A.6 Leisure time activities

Multiple responses were allowed. The main activities of the respondents are their hobbies (63.6%) and the household (52.5%), followed by childcare (37.0%), taking part in educational programmes (32.7%), voluntary work (20.4%) and care for Family members (16.0%).

Part B: EDUCATION

B.1 Digital activities of the respondents

The respondents gave the following answers concerning their digital activities:

82.7% of the survey participants own a PC, 77.8% use their PC without help of others, 4.9% need help with their PC.

22.8% of the respondents own a tablet, 22.2% use it without help, 1.9% with help.

45.1% of the survey participants own a smartphone, 43.2% use it without the help of others, 1.9% need help.

In addition to that, 2 respondents mentioned that they rarely use their computers and do neither own a tablet nor smartphone.

51.9% of the participants use a “normal” mobile phone.

B.2 Getting to know about the Seniorenkolleg

75.9% of the interviewed persons answered, that they were informed by their family or friends about the educational offers of the Seniorenkolleg (word-of-mouth). 19.8% through the newspaper, 3.1% through advertisements.

B.3 Main motivation for participation in educational offers

As the main motivation for the visit of the Seniorenkolleg almost all respondents (97.5%) call generally new knowledge and information. 42.0% want to gain knowledge for practical use in their everyday lives, 69.1% are looking for background information about current events. 66.0% are viewing the participation in the Seniorenkolleg as important for their personal development; 46.3% are happy to get to know other people and to broaden their social networks. Other reasons are: the transfer of obtained knowledge to others, e.g. other seniors or the younger generation, and having a meaningful pastime.

B.4 Start of first educational activities at the Seniorenkolleg

The 28.4% of respondents has participated in the educational activities of the Seniorenkolleg for more than 5 years; 11.7% are part of the Seniorenkolleg for over 15 years. 4.3% of the respondents started attending in the last semester.

B.5 Satisfaction with the educational programmes

The statement: "The educational programme, which I participated in, was according to my expectations." was fully agreed to by 12.3%. 50.0% agreed with the statement, and 32.7% agreed partially. No one disagreed. 4.9% did not answer.

B.6 Reasons for not attending educational activities (*Lectures, Courses, Excursions*), multiple answers – the main reasons:

- Lack of time (courses 16.7%, lectures and courses each 11.7%)
- No interesting subjects (lectures 14.8%, excursions 7.4%, courses 2.5%)
- Personal circumstances other than health (courses 8.6%, excursions 7.4%, lectures 5.6%)
- Health issues (courses 8.4%, excursions 7.4%, lectures 5.6%)

Remarkable: Financial reasons (excursions (3.1%), courses (0.6%))

B.7 Participation in the next semester?

Nearly all of the respondents (95.1%) are planning to attend the Seniorenkolleg in the next semester.

B.8 Reasons for not participating in the next semester

Reasons that were only named isolated (only by 1 person each):
lack of time, health issues, topics, that interest me are not being offered,
personal reasons

B.9 Number of attended semesters

Most of the respondents attended 6 semesters in the Seniorenkolleg (7.4%), followed by 2, 10 and 12 semesters (4.9% each) as well as 20 semesters (4.3%), 26 Semesters (3.1%), 36 Semesters (1.9%) and 38 Semesters (1.2%). 0.6% of the respondents attended the Seniorenkolleg for 40, 43 or 46 semesters each.

B.10 Attended semesters per year

The vast majority (88.3 %) of the respondents answered that they attend two semesters (summer and winter semester) per year. Furthermore, 1.9 % attends one semester per year. The remaining 9.3% refrained from answering this question.

B.11 Preferred topics of lectures

The population was asked to name their preferred topics for educational purposes. The answers show the wide range of interest, though one can see that the topic of science (67.9%) and the topics of art and culture (66.7%), followed by health (61.18%), medicine (61.1%), economy (56.8%), technology (54.3%), politics (53.7%), society (48.8%), history of art (48.1%), history / archaeology (45.1%), architecture (43.8%), psychology/sociology / anthropology (40.7%).

Other mention: world politics, astronomy, nature.

B.13 Preferred time slots to attend an educational programme

Almost all respondents (94.4%) prefer to take part in educational programs during the day and on week days. After 17:00 hours only 5.5% want to attend, on weekends merely 1.2%. 0.6% do not care about the time it takes place.

B.12 und B.14 are not relevant for Chemnitz

B.15 Arrival and education venues

50.6% of respondents prefer to visit an education programme in their own city or the place where they live. 43.8% would accept up to an hour of arrival to the place of education. 8.0% of the respondents only participate in courses they can get to within 30 minutes. For 10.5% an easy arrival is especially important, for 6.8% the travel expenses are crucial.

B.16 Criteria / Sequence of importance for choosing educational offers

1. Topic
2. Quality of the educational programme
3. Day and time
4. Participation of friends and acquaintances
5. Accessibility of the venue
6. Equipment for my health problem
7. Presenter/teacher

8. Excursions
9. Fees
10. Duration per lecture/ class, e.g. 90 mins
11. Duration of the lecture series/ course, e.g. 14 weeks
12. Venue/ acoustics at the venue
13. Participants

Conclusions

162 attendees of the Seniorenkolleg at the TU Chemnitz took part in the survey of the EduSenNet project. With 1,000 participants in a semester this is a rate of about 16 percent. Based on this survey as well as previous surveys and studies in the Seniorenkolleg the following **results and conclusions** regarding the further work and development of the Seniorenkolleg can be drawn:

- Starting with 150 participants in the year of founding the attendance numbers increased strongly. The educational offers of the Seniorenkolleg are currently being used by approximately 1,000 elders. The number of attendees during the summer semester is slightly below the number of the winter semester. Main reasons that were being named are: garden work and travels.
- A high percentage of the interviewees (38%) is living alone and is looking for – like 46% of the interviewees in total – opportunities to socialize with other elders who have similar interests next to the participation in educational offers. The resulting social networks among older people even have an effect on their private lives and are very important for mutual support in many areas of life (help with PC problems, with ailments etc.). These networks also lead to joint leisure activities and even new partnerships.
- The relatively low number of elders without final studies degree in the Seniorenkolleg requires special activities to win over new participants out of this group. This requires low-threshold educational offers with application oriented knowledge and easily understandable language. For this reason the label "lecture" was changed into "presentations", to reduce inhibition thresholds for attending.
- The analysis shows a high share of participants with long-term attendance of the Seniorenkolleg (10, 15, 20 years). They "aged" with the Seniorenkolleg and belong to the main age group of 71-80 years (51.2%). Their contentedness with the Seniorenkolleg is to be seen as

positive, on the other side this result implies an urgent necessity to win over younger seniors at the transition to the phase of life after work. In the near future it is planned to recruit more older people that are still working to motivate them to participate in educational offers during this interim phase. Surveys show, that especially men are relatively unprepared regarding their retirement from work in comparison to women. Presentations to motivate to pursue education, modules for the transition from occupation to the so called "retirement", to point up possibilities for useful activities and incentive to attend the Seniorenkolleg, are planned.

- The advertising efforts in the media and the press work for information about the Seniorenkolleg and for winning over new participants, especially younger elders, are to be increased (e.g. to display informational material, flyer, programme in pharmacies, medical and veterinary practices).
- More than one third of the participants of the Seniorenkolleg are taking care of their grandchildren in their free time, especially to support the working parents. This tendency is increasing as well. This important care function is developing more and more into an educational task. Educated grandparents are able to transfer knowledge to their grandchildren and to enable them to "discover and help to form the world". On the other hand the elders become receivers of knowledge too, through cross-generational learning processes (exchange of knowledge, e.g. PC usage). This also benefits the personality development of the elders.
- Many participants are volunteering in their free time or pursue interesting leisure activities, which they are presenting in the Seniorenkolleg. These possibilities are being used. Once per semester a participant of a task group of the Seniorenkolleg is doing a presentation as the speaker.
- The most popular lecture topics are from the fields of science, art and culture, health/medicine and economics, technology and politics. Besides the information in general the elders are trying to gather knowledge that aids them in their daily lives. Previous surveys showed, that the trend from theoretical communication of knowledge to additional application-oriented education, knowledge that is useful for elders in everyday life, is magnified. Through this trend educationally alienated target groups and elders without a university degree are able

to reduce possible inhibition thresholds and obtain access to this form of education.

- After evaluating the survey we increased the share of application-oriented lectures, to exceed the mere communication of knowledge. As a result, the elders experience the benefit of these educational offers first-hand. The number of educational excursions has been raised as well, to enable the participants to study the implementations with examples of good practice on site after the lectures. Besides the lectures of the Seniorenkolleg, which are mentioned by nearly all the participants, about two third of the survey participants are using the educational excursions to deepen the contents of the lectures on site or in praxis. The demand is increasing.
- For new participants of the Seniorenkolleg lectures concerning culture and cultural education are much in demand for, e.g. with topics like classical music, theatre i.a., to pick the elders up at their interests.
- The freedom from barriers/accessibility is being named as an important criterion for participation by survey participants. This includes: wheelchair-accessible avenues, disability-friendly equipment, comfortable seating, hearing aids and sign language interpreters for special presentations.
- Use of tour guide systems for educational excursions, to improve auditory abilities.
- The survey participants increasingly have a high degree of media-related expertise (media usage). They use PC, tablet and smartphone in various ways and apply their skills practically in everyday life. This makes it possible to implement new methods of transferring educational knowledge, e.g. Feedback Apps on the participants Smartphones in the lecture hall for an immediate presentation of the answers to questions and opinions or even livestream use from home while preventing attendance on site.
- In rural regions we support local players with our experience in developing new educational programmes. At the same time we offer up the possibility to community centres and other institutions to receive selected presentations of the Seniorenkolleg of the TU Chemnitz via livestream on the Internet with video (including the lecturer and the PowerPoint presentation) and audio material. At once, it is possible to take part in the discussion in the auditorium of the TU Chemnitz by using e-mail.

- About one fourth of the participants of the Seniorenkolleg are from rural regions. The survey showed, that an uncomplicated arrival especially holds importance for them. To heighten this percentage, means of public transport are to be improved, especially in the villages (local government level, public transport companies). Further possibilities include the establishment of private lift-sharing to get to the venue of the Seniorenkolleg. It is also important to provide enough parking spaces at the venue.
- The interest in participating in additional activities of the Seniorenkolleg, like ERASMUS project work or contributing to a task group is increasing. At the moment there are seniors working in two ERASMUS+ project groups and in two task groups for politics and innovation:

Task group politics: co-creation of social processes, presentation of the results in the lectures, participating in panel discussions with policymakers and economical decision makers -

Because the demand for political education is just sparsely developed, cooperations with the political senior delegations, especially on the local government level, but also state level, were made and instead of lectures panel discussions, e.g. regarding local politics topics, were organized. In the context of educational excursions there was an exchange of experiences over coffee and cake with members of the seniors' delegations and local politicians on site. In this way it was also possible to increase the interest in political education. A group of active seniors was found, that discusses political topics every two weeks and documents their expectations towards the politicians. It is planned to win this group over to arrange a joint panel discussion with politicians and seniors in preparation for the parliamentary elections for the Bundestag in 2017. Members of this task group participated in the official federal event regarding the "Internationalen Tag der älteren Menschen" ("International day of the older people") for the first time in Magdeburg on the 01.10.2016.

Task group innovation/product development: contribution to product development for the target group of elders (kitchen technology), contributing expertise, also out of former professional life -

Participants also show interest in supporting the Seniorenkolleg as volunteers at an increasing rate. Possibilities to do that are when deciding

the programme in the spokesmen-council or regarding the organisation (access control, cloakroom service).

The results of the EduSenNet-Project and our experiences with motivation and active learning tasks of elders regarding cultural, scientific and political education will be presented, in cooperation with our project partners, in the context of an international conference in June 2017 at the TU Chemnitz, to attending politicians and advanced vocational trainers to the transfer the results. We will relay our results as a recommendation to regional facilities (churches, clubs, meeting venues and civic centres) as well.

7.6. Magdeburg

SURVEY AMONG THE OLDER STUDENTS

Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg

(Olaf Freyemark / Annika Rathmann)

Lifelong Learning 50+ has been offered at the Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg for over 20 years and is focused at senior adults who would like to be engaged with science.

Figure 1: Participant development of *Lifelong Learning 50+* – absolute frequencies

Source: *Lifelong Learning 50+* at the Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg

The concept of *Lifelong Learning 50+* has been integrated at the Education and Media Research Department, with focus on Continuous Education at the Institute of Science Education, Faculty of Human Sciences. The program is open to all 50+ adults interested in continuous education and lifelong learning. Secondary school diploma is not required. *Lifelong Learning 50+* can be enrolled with a visitor status, which allows participation in public lectures offered by all faculties. Since 2004 project-based work has been employed and become a strong focus of the program. The objective was to bring together students of various ages and engaged them in collaborative research. In this way the organizers bring to life the motto of Senior Studies "Young and elderly study together" and this is still our requirement today. Since the beginning of *Lifelong Learning 50+* the number of participants has steadily been increasing (see Fig. 1). At the very beginning, during the Winter Semester 1991/92, there were 12 people enrolled. 25 years later, the provisional peak has been reached during the Winter Semester 2015/16, with a participation quota of 718 people. In order to supply tailored, group-oriented offers and intensify collaborative work according among program participants, based on a variety of interests, several studies have been carried out. In the following contribution a survey on senior students from the Summer Semester 2014 will be presented.

Detailed findings are accessible in: Freymark, Olaf (ed.): *Continuous Science Education for Adults. Past - Present - Future, Dedicated to the 25th anniversary of Lifelong Learning 50+*, Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg, p. 17- 43.

a) Rationale and Methodological Aspects

The following issues and topic areas which provide data about the current situation of senior education at the Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg as well as specific indicators for an in-depth development of *Lifelong Learning 50+* are crucial to the study:

- How program participants rate the educational offer for senior students?
- What reasons motivate them to attend the program and what is their particular interest?

- What kind of program aspects make them feel satisfied and which improvements do they wish?

The quantitative survey has been designed using partially standardized questionnaires. Each questionnaire comprises four pages and can be answered in ca. 10 minutes. In the learning program, all *Lifelong Learning 50+* participants from the Summer Semester 2014 were targeted to be involved. The survey had been announced at Semester inauguration. Questionnaires were issued by the *Lifelong Learning 50+* office and distributed during the enrollment procedure, particularly at well attended events; the questionnaires could be returned personally or dropped in the mailbox. In addition to that, a round mail was sent via mailing lists of senior students to all participants. 247 from 532 enrolled senior students actively participated in the survey, which corresponds to ca. 46 per cent.

b) Selected Results

The respondents were mostly interested in special events, trips and visits and open lectures at all faculties. More than half of all respondents clearly expressed their interests (see fig. 2). The introductory events which mark the beginning of Summer and Winter Semesters usually are accompanied by thematic lectures, match with the interests of well two-thirds of the respondents. Traditional academic forms, e.g. lectures and seminars, foreign language courses, computer courses and library introductions were estimated as less interesting by the interviewed, compared to other program forms. Nonetheless, a large group of respondents also expressed their interest in these offers.

Definitely, history is the topic area participants are mostly interested in. More than two-thirds of all respondents indicate this discipline (see Figure 3).

Considering the expressed interests, History is followed by Art Studies. Psychology comes third, followed by the topic group Political / Social Sciences / Sociology and Philosophy. Nearly one third of all interviewed are passionately interested in the last topic.

Figure 2: Interest in various courses and events of Lifelong Learning 50+ (N 247) – numbers in per cent

Question: To what extent are you interested in the following event type? Response form as indicated.

Source: Survey of the participants from *Lifelong Learning 50+*, Summer Semester 2014

Figure 3: Interest in various disciplines (N 247) - numbers in per cent

Question: Which disciplines are you mostly interested in? (Multiple Choice set)

Source: Survey of participants from *Lifelong Learning 50+*, Summer Semester 2014

According to the survey, a strong focus has been highlighted on certain topic areas, such as Literary Studies, Linguistics, Medicine, Religious Studies as well as Mathematics and Natural Sciences. Between 20 per

cent and 30 per cent of all respondents have expressed interest in these disciplines. Other topic areas did not receive sufficient coverage. Various disciplines are mentioned under 'Miscellaneous'. These comprise, for example, Sports and Sport Studies, Education Studies, Media Studies or Musicology.

What deserves attention is the fact that in all those cases the topic preferences appeared to be gender-related. There is a significant difference between men's and women's preferences in the survey results, as evidenced in ten out of thirteen topic areas (see Figure 4). Men are often more interested in Political / Social Sciences / Sociology, Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Economics, Engineering, and History. Women, on the other hand, are significantly more interested in Art, Literature, Psychology, Medicine and Linguistics. Particularly strong gender differences are visible in the field of Arts and Humanities. Gender-related differences appear to be less relevant in the area of Language Studies, although they are still significant.

Figure 4: Interest in disciplines by gender (N 247) – numbers in per cent

Question: Which disciplines are you mostly interested in? A Multiple Choice set with 14 response options (13 topic areas and others). Presented are only disciplines with gender-related significant differences (Chi²-Tests, *p ≤ .05). Ranking starts with the largest difference between subgroups.

Source: Survey of participants from *Lifelong Learning 50+*, Summer Semester 2014

A high level of satisfaction prevails generally among participants from the offered *Lifelong Learning 50+* program. Every second respondent states that they are mostly satisfied, while further 46 per cent express unconditional satisfaction (see Fig. 5). Only three per cent of the participants say that they are neither satisfied, nor dissatisfied.

In two open questions at the end of the questionnaire, the participants had the opportunity to highlight particularly good aspects and to point out possibilities for improvement. The interviewed took the opportunity to genuinely express their personal desires. As a whole, 184 of 247 people (= 74.5 per cent) commented what they really liked about *Lifelong Learning 50+*.

Above all, respondents emphasize the diversity and wide range of offers from which they can choose according to their own interests, as well as the new knowledge and insights, but also the establishment of new social contacts. For example, participants point out the "wide range of diversity, challenging events and a high level of offered courses" (case 44), "many excursions and a variety of topics" (case 55).

Figure 5: Overall satisfaction with *Lifelong Learning 50+* (N 247) - numbers in per cent

Question: Overall, how satisfied are you with *Lifelong Learning 50+*? Response form as indicated.

Source: Survey of participants from *Lifelong Learning 50+*, Summer Semester 2014

Participants also state that they "learn new things, deepen their knowledge, as well as get enriched with new social contacts" (case 182) and acquire "new knowledge and insights" (case 183); they "have a goal

in mind [...] [and] stimulate the gray cells running" (case 131). However, the opportunity to participate in the regular study program and thus get in touch with younger ones is particularly attractive for the participants in Lifelong Learning 50+, as proved by the following quotations: "elderly and young together" (case 139), "age mixture of students" (case 215), "participation in lectures with quite usual, young students" (case 68), "connecting students from *Lifelong Learning 50+* to regular studies" (case 190). In addition, attention is focused on the good services provided by the *Lifelong Learning 50+* team, which delivers "precise information" (case 230) and ensures a "good organization" (case 115). A total of **111 from 247 respondents** (44.9 per cent) offer ideas for further improvements of the *Lifelong Learning 50+* program. The interviewed are particularly concerned about the future of the Human Sciences Faculty resp. future course offers, which is still open as the following quotations indicate: "The Arts and Humanities' Faculties should not be closed!" (case 244) "If there are no human sciences, *Lifelong Learning 50+* will belong to the past. This would be a disaster!" (case 219), "It is crucial to preserve the course offers in philosophy (human rights) and history" (case 216). Moreover, respondents expressed specific proposals concerning organizational and content changes. In addition to the improvement of technical equipment ("more microphones", case 138), they insisted on boosting of public relation activities (e.g. in the press) as well as on increasing the attractiveness of Internet presence of the *Lifelong Learning 50+* program ("with current changes, indications - to be easier accessible, case 126). The allocation of places for excursions needs to be addressed more frequently. Respondents wish that "a longer list of places would be available for regional and interregional visits (Case 59); excursion participation should be available for new and former participants" (case 26). The number of participants should not be fixed in advance, if possible." (case 116). They also propose to develop further the "work in project groups" (case 92) or to activate more fields of "discussion between regular and senior students" (case 220). Overall, a high level of satisfaction among program participants has been also evidenced concerning the above-mentioned question. Many respondents say that they have no suggestions for further improvements and that they are completely satisfied: "everything is optimal" (case 201), "It is desirable that these studying opportunities are preserved for a long time" (case 156).

c) Summary

To sum up, the participants express a high level of satisfaction with the *Lifelong Learning 50+* program. They are particularly interested in events such as excursions and sightseeing tours, organized especially for guests. The offers deriving from regular courses at the faculties are the third point. The focus of thematic interest lies clearly on History, along with other topic areas. Art Studies and Psychology follow suit within the ranking of topic areas. The interests of participants are also mirrored in the actual assignments. Courses in History, Art History and with regional topics proved to be among the most popular. Gender-related comparison indicates that men are somewhat more interested in Political and Social Sciences, Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Economics and Engineering. Women, on the other hand, are more often interested in Art, Literature, Psychology, Medicine, and Linguistics.

As motives for participation in the *Lifelong Learning 50+* program, respondents clearly identify the maintenance of mental fitness, the expansion of general education and satisfaction of their own educational pursuit. The opportunity to continue their education in the former professions and improve professional qualification for post-employment or voluntary activity, are significant only for a small group. The motive of "making a youth dream come true" which has often been discussed within the context of "continuous education" for senior students and which has long been considered as a particularly relevant drive for educational participation, is obviously of secondary significance, compared to other motivation. If results from earlier surveys at the university are also used to be compared with the current ones, a great consistency of participation reasons is to be highlighted.

Collaborative learning of senior and regular students is considered unproblematic by both target groups. There is hardly any evidence concerning conflict points. However, social contacts and interaction usually remain on the surface or are sporadically experienced. Respondents expressed the desire for more exchange opportunities and collaborative projects. Previously existing initiatives could be expanded even further. Other suggestions for improvement, which have been brought by participants of the *Lifelong Learning 50+*, are mostly related to

organizational aspects, for example, how the organization of enrollment week should be managed, as well as concerns about a sufficient Internet program presence and the development public relation activities. There are also specific indications to optimize the *Lifelong Learning 50+* program.

7.7. Uppsala

Learning in later life at Uppsala Senioruniversitet

(Compiled in February 2017 by Dr Maj Aldskogius and Dr Björn Odin)

As a first part of this project we carried out a survey about seniors who were not members of Uppsala Senioruniversitet. The results from this survey were first presented in a separate progress report, "*Learning in later life for people 50*" (February 2016).

In this second part we have been carried out a survey designed to obtain basic information that will make it possible to plan suitable measures and proposals to ensure that seniors who are engaged in educational activities at Uppsala Senioruniversitet can benefit from our educational programmes and other activities regardless of background, present living situation or mobility.

This national report will first of all provide basic data useful for further development of the program at Uppsala Senioruniversitet. The Swedish original version has mainly been prepared by Maj Aldskogius and the English version is compiled by Björn Odin.

The Survey

In September 2016 Uppsala Senioruniversitet (USU) had 3,810 registered members and all members have a membership number. The oldest members have the lowest numbers and new members have the highest numbers.

To be able to draw conclusions from this survey that can be useful in planning future activities in our U3A it was important for us get a random sample of all the members. We decided to address a sample of 10% of the members. The sample consists of 381 people which we decided was enough. We chose a systematic sample of every tenth member starting

with a random number from 0 to 9. In this way we also knew that both very old and very new members would be included.

Only 9% of the members of the sample did not have an email address. We therefore decided to send the questionnaires by e-mail from USUs office. The people chosen were asked to complete the questionnaire and send it back by e-mail. Detailed instructions on how to do that were given. If they still were not able to return the questionnaire by mail, they were asked to send an e-mail or call the USU office and they would then get the questionnaire by regular mail with a stamped return envelope with USUs address. The 36 people which did not have an e-mail address and another 20 who could not read the attachment got the questionnaire by mail.

The USU office staff then sent a reminder to all those that had got the questionnaire by another email and made telephone calls to those who had got it by regular mail. After all this work only 45% of the people in the sample had answered which we decided was by far too few. We had to realize that we had misjudged computer skills of our members. Even if they had an email address many could not handle attachments. We therefore decided to send new questionnaires by regular mail to the 200 that had not answered and gave them a new deadline.

After this action almost 80% had answered but we were still not satisfied. Some of those that did not answer had specifically said that they did not want to answer. Some were too old and some were new members that had not had time to take part in anything yet and had nothing to report, others did not like surveys per se. We then asked the members in the international committee if they could call 10–12 people each, namely the ones that had not answered at all, to see if some of them would do that. We got another 25 answers and we then had 329 answers all together, 86% of the total sample, which was even more that we had expected. But we had to work hard to get this result!

Three people from the project group have then coded all the 329 answers and one of the technical staff has provided us with the results in total numbers and percentages. For all questions we have noted all that have not answered that specific question. Only one question has very few answers: the number of attended activities last year

Results, Conclusions and reflections

The USU students - who are they

All respondents are living in Sweden but a few are born in another country – mainly in Europe and often in our neighbouring countries like Finland.

In Uppsala we have quite a number of inhabitants who are not born in the Nordic countries and some of them are now seniors. Since many years more than half of the population growth in Sweden is linked to immigration. These immigrants are now Swedish citizens but very few of them are members of the USU. When we made this observation the project team started to discuss how to engage those people in education activities. The institutions within the EduSenNet have tried different ways to reach them, but this has been a difficult task. In a separate paper, Ulla Myhrman describes these efforts, plans and ideas about how to proceed. Innovations like this take time to implement. One of the most crucial factors is to find the right contact people in different groups of people with very varying cultural backgrounds. This innovative process has started in the USU and will hopefully continue even after the end of the EduSenNet project.

Most of the members are living in Uppsala and most of them have a university degree. Less than 10% are not living in the city itself. From an earlier survey of non-members (February 2016) we know that many people outside Uppsala do not feel “at home” with an organisation labelled “University”. At the same time there are a number of study organisations with a long tradition of organizing educational activities all over Sweden, which many people are more familiar with than the USU.

Most the USU members live in their own flats/houses, only a few live in residential homes of different kinds.

There is a noticeable gender imbalance in the group of respondents (67% are women), but this reflects very well the overall situation in the USU, which in the context of the present study means that the sample is representative of the population - all the USU members. Not much has happened over the years, and different initiatives have been taken to attract more men. But it must of course be remembered that women in general live about five years longer than men. But the question is perhaps something that the board might have to discuss more: “Do we have a program that is more attractive to women?”

Age distribution is the following:

Age:	Number of answers	%
a) 50 – 60 years old	1	0
b) 61 – 70	116	35
c) 71 – 80	166	50
d) 81 – 90	36	11
e) 91 +	6	2

Fifty percent of the respondents are between 71 and 80 years of age. Some are as old as 91+ and only one person is younger than 61. We know from other statistics that the average age among the USU members is 74 years. Compared to other U3As in different countries the USU members are older than students from other universities. Lifelong learning is attractive even at a high age!

More than 87% of the students have an academic degree or an equivalent educational background. This is both positive and demanding when it comes to the quality of education activities offered by the USU.

The respondents were asked to place three of the mentioned activities in order of preference: 1. Most important (Pri 1), 2. Second most important (Pri 2), 3. Third most important (Pri 3). The following diagram 1. shows the distribution of answers:

Diagram 1: Activities beside USU

Even though the average age is high among the respondents there are some who still carry out full or part time work. Many of the respondents mention care for grandchildren as the most important activity in their spare time, besides different hobbies. Voluntary work and activities in clubs and societies are other typical traditional Swedish activities for people of this generation which are ranked high among important activities in their spare time.

The USU students – experiences and ideas about learning

The respondents were asked if they had access to and used different digital tools. As a follow up question they were asked whether they needed assistance or not to be able to use the tool.

Digital tool:	% with access	% who need assistance
a) Computer	93	18
b) Ipad	44	4
c) Smartphone	68	7
d) Other mobile phone	30	7

More than 90% of the respondents have access to a computer and have an email address. But when it comes to the practical use many people could not fill in and send back a questionnaire by email. The same goes for smartphones; 68% have one but a few of them need assistance to be able to use it fully. This indicates that there is a need for training in how to use computers and smartphones. Probably many people now get assistance from children/grandchildren and friends when needed, but it would be recommendable that courses in this were available as was the case earlier within the USU program until a new generation is joining the USU, with better digital knowledge than the present members.

Most respondents got their first contact with the USU via family or friends, but some got it via the internet or the USU brochure. This indicates that the brochure has a certain value for the first contact, but it is probably more a question of how it is diffused and where it is available. It is astonishing that so few have got information via Uppsala University or the University of Agriculture. Maybe this has to do with an overall lack of information nowadays about “getting retired” and different opportunities for being active as a retired person. Very few organisations have any elaborated information or courses about retirement when their employees

are approaching retirement. Maybe it could be possible for the USU to offer some sort of short courses for people who are soon going to be retired. Probably this can be done in close cooperation with other organisations for seniors.

The respondents were asked about their main motives for engaging in educational activities. The following diagram 2. shows the distribution of answers:

Diagram 2: Main motives for engaging in educational activities

The survey indicates that most people are motivated to gain new knowledge and insights in order to further personal development as seniors. Most of them attended their first education activity at the USU 2 to 9 years ago and many have been active for a long period after retirement. People who have started to study at the USU often continue, and the fact that many new members have joined the USU during the last few years must be looked upon as a positive assessment of the USU activities. It is also encouraging that as many as 88% of the respondents are of the opinion that the attended education activities have completely, or to a relatively high degree, matched their expectations.

Matching degree:	Number of answers	%
a) Completely	99	30
b) To a relatively high degree	191	58
c) Partly	18	5
d) Not at all	1	0

The reasons for not attending the USU activities of course vary a good deal. The time factor is the dominating and limiting one. Either people lack the time or the hours of the activity do not suit them. For most members health and economy are not any limiting factors.

This question was only put to those that did not take part in any activities last year. The question was: "If you did not attend USU activities, what was the reason?" The following diagram 3. shows the distribution of answers:

Diagram 3: Reasons not to attend USU activities

To try to make it possible for more members to take part an experimental test project has been developed as an innovation linked to the

EduSenNet project, under the name of the “film project”. Per Olof Osterman who is the person in the project team in charge of the film project will report about it in a separate paper. During the project all “Tuesday lectures” have been filmed and members have - during a period of 14 days - the possibility to see it in their own computer or together with others in a more organised way. By the “film project” the time factor has become much less critical for many people. The time factor was also dominating for people who planned to take part in USU education activities in 2016/17.

In 2015/16 most of the active members attended one or two lecture series during the year, but a few attended three and even four series. In the case of study circles most people had attended one or two circles during the same period of time. In the case of study trips people normally did not join more than one or two. Relatively many people also attended Tuesday lectures - which take place every second week.

People attend approximately the same number of activities throughout the years, but as they get older – and possibly become more tired – not so many continue with as many activities as before.

The respondents were asked which of a number of subjects were of most interest to them. They were also asked to make a priority list between the subjects by ticking three of them. Here is the sum of pri 1, pri 2 and pri 3 of their priorities:

Subject*:	Ticked by x number of persons:	% of all answers
a) Human sciences	185	19
b) Religion	155	16
c) Language	103	10
d) Natural sciences	150	15
e) Literature	245	25
f) Economy	32	3
g) Other subject	20	2
h) No answer	97	10

- Human sciences including psychology, sociology and law. Religion + philosophy and history. Languages (classic and modern languages). Natural sciences includes technical sciences and medicine. Literature + arts and music. Among other subjects, politics and environment are mentioned.

The subject/topic of activities are of course very important when people choose between different activities. Literature, art and music are the most popular/interesting subjects among the respondents, followed by social sciences and religion. In social sciences we include psychology, sociology and law. Many people are also interested in natural sciences, technical sciences and medicine and almost as many people are interested in learning modern or classic languages. The USU, situated in a city with two universities, is in a fortunate position with many professional and well-known lecturers available in different subjects, which makes it possible to offer a wide scope of educational activities in most subjects.

The respondents were asked to tell when they would prefer to attend an activity and also to tick alternatives (pri 1, pri 2, and pri 3). The following table shows their priorities:

Period	Priority 1		Priority 2		Priority 3	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Weekdays in daytime as now	320	97	2	1	1	0
Weekdays in the evening	4	1	99	30	11	3
Weekends	1	0	23	7	26	8
Summer course	0	0	9	3	30	9
No answer	4	1	179	54	205	63

The USU has traditionally carried out the different activities on weekdays in daytime, and this is also what most people prefer. A vast majority want the lecture series to last for $6 \times 2 = 12$ hours as is the case today. The study circles are either $6 \times 2 = 12$ hours in most subjects but twice as many hours in languages ($12 \times 2 = 24$ hours) as this is what most people seem to want even if other alternatives are mentioned by some.

The respondents were asked which factors were most important regarding the location of an education activity.

Factor:	Number of answers	%
a) Distance to location	80	24
b) Public transport facilities	65	20
c) Transport time	5	2
d) Transport cost	5	2
e) Audio/hearing quality	72	22
f) Audio/hearing aids available	23	7
g) Visual quality of pictures shown	34	10
h) Other factors	13	4
i) No answer	32	10

Distance to the location of an education activity together with the availability of public transport are the most important factors when a person is considering whether to take part in an activity. Costs and time for transport to a certain location are not mentioned as important factors. It is much more important that the venue has good audio-visual facilities. The respondents were asked to rank the three most important factors for the choice of an education activity. (Diagram 4.)

Diagram 4: Most important factors for the choice of an activity

The subject is the most important factor behind the choice of an education activity. This factor is mentioned by 83% of the respondents. The second most important factor mentioned was the lecturer. The USU is fortunate in having many highly qualified lecturers and some who consistently draw quite large audiences. The third most important factor is the weekday and the time of day. It is remarkable that very few respondents mention that they attend an activity just because a friend does so too. The social factor is important but it apparently does not affect the choice of activities that much. The cost factor is not important for our members. This is partly due to the fact that the USU can keep the fees low thanks to the work of about 80 volunteers.

8. INNOVATION OF THE STUDY OFFER

8.1. What are the most relevant topics / priorities addressed by the project?

1. Facilitating the validation of non-formal and informal learning and its permeability with formal education pathways

2. New innovative curricula/educational methods / development of training courses

- Each of included institutions hopes to improve the weak position of the elderly education by learning from best practices in other countries and promote learning partnerships on a European level.
- The project brings scale of information about educational programs for people over 50 in other European countries and the possibilities for formal learning of the elderly besides the non-formal educational programs. It shows the ways to innovate and design study programs for people over 50 in new subjects.
- Project extends awareness of information about the own the UTA's non-formal and informal learning activities for the elderly to the city communities, residential homes or in rural areas.

Extension of the information encourages elderly with low skills and not involved in the education to register for new study possibilities.

- New learning methods described in the project can be used for new groups of elderly students in some rural areas and city communities.
- Contacts and research between the groups of the elderly as with young students can support health environment at the universities, better understanding and acceptance at the university background.

Innovations focus on:

- new study subjects since the project have started;
- new places (areas, regions) for learning (communities);
- new groups of students, number of new students, gender changes , educational level;
- new methods in learning.

9. INNOVATION OF THE STUDY OFFER AND BEST PRACTICES OF THE PROJECT INSTITUTIONS

9.1. ALICANTE

APAE Programme: “Support to the prevention of school absenteeism”

Author/s	Permanent University of the University of Alicante – Education Department (Alicante Town Council)
Title	APAE Programme: ‘Support to the prevention of school absenteeism’
Keywords	Support of older adults to prevent school absenteeism amongst youngsters
Context – location and	The University of Alicante hosts the ‘Incubator of Values,’ an initiative of over-50 students enrolled in

<p>impact</p>	<p>the <i>Diploma Senior</i> of the Permanent University, and interested in lifelong learning and personal development, who have long been involved in EU projects. They wished to dedicate part of their time to help other seniors and share both their accumulated and their newly-acquired knowledge with other seniors in these times of economic crisis and lack of values, which have resulted in many citizens needing the support of these UPUA volunteers. Based on this approach, a wide variety of initiatives have been set in motion since 2012, including volunteering actions to promote active and healthy ageing, technological volunteering, cultural volunteering (collaborative conversation-based language; study of literature and poetry groups; theatre groups); and social-research-oriented volunteering (Observatory of Seniors and Mass Media). Along the same lines, a new initiative APAE Programme: 'Support to the prevention of school absenteeism' arose in 2015.</p> <p>The Alicante Town Council and the University of Alicante are collaborating in several activities focused on educational development, intergenerational solidarity, social cohesion, volunteering and lifelong learning and beneficial to every citizen of Alicante.</p> <p>Education is undoubtedly essential for human beings and the society they live in, firstly, as a process of maturity and individual self-improvement aimed at achieving personal autonomy and, secondly, as a social evolution process.</p> <p>Faced with the need to fight against social exclusion as well to achieve economic and social progress, it is our duty to ensure that every individual will receive at least some basic education so that the situation in terms of social development can improve.</p> <p>Efforts have long been made from the Education Department of the Alicante Town Council in the fight against absenteeism, school dropout and being out of school, in and around Alicante town.</p> <p>The UPUA provides training to over-50s seeking to favour personal development, as well as social integration, and to promote active citizenship as a</p>
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	<p>way to improve quality of life and promote healthy ageing. Other aims include: stimulating older adults no longer professionally active to reorient their lives and feel more useful at a family, community and country level; promoting, recognising and enriching the experiences acquired by seniors in their life; and encouraging individuals with a long personal and professional experience to reflect on it from a new theoretical-practical perspective.</p>
Start date	October 2015
Institution	Permanent University of the University of Alicante – Education Department (Alicante Town Council)
Addressees	<p>a) Older adults: UPUA students who offer as volunteers to give school support sessions (lectures-tutorials-mentoring).</p> <p>b) School children and teenagers helped by the APAE Programme: 6-to-16-year-old students from every Alicante quarter/district, lacking in resources and at risk of social exclusion and school absenteeism, who are referred to this programme from the educational centres to the Local Departments of Social Action and Education.</p>
Thematic area	Education, Social Action, Intergenerationality, Volunteering, Active Ageing
Justification	<p>A considerable number of the students who attend school in the compulsory education stages (over 150) comprised between the ages of 6 to 16 who become involved in school absenteeism processes mainly due to the lack of resources in their families. This entails a high risk of social exclusion and may eventually result in serious problems for their future life.</p> <p>A significant proportion of Permanent University students are retired teachers willing to collaborate on a voluntary, altruistic basis in actions linked to training and socio-educational projection.</p> <p>It is important to: (a) optimise these intergenerational and transversal cooperation initiatives for the promotion of a cohesive, intergenerational and inclusive society; (b) encourage active ageing; and</p>

	(c) ensure the existence of an informed young generation that can complete basic education and schooling goals and levels.
Objectives	Offering extracurricular support for students in need, to offset their lacks and help them to: (a) achieve their academic goals; (b) prevent school absenteeism; (c) promote intergenerational solidarity; (d) encourage active ageing; and (e) promote an inclusive society by means of education and intergenerational practices.
Experience	<p>This programme has been developed during the academic years 2015-2016 and 2016-2017 with an annual average of 80-100 students and 15-20 older adult volunteers. All these students attended two 90-to-120-minute-long extracurricular evening sessions held in municipal and community centres.</p> <p>The School Absenteeism Department of the Alicante Town Council and the Permanent University coordinated and organized this programme.</p> <p>Advertising is made at educational centres and possible beneficiaries are also detected through social workers. As for UPUA, it also holds informative sessions. A mailing and an online questionnaire are used to assign the different groups.</p> <p>Both social workers and the School Absenteeism Department, together with UPUA, subsequently carry out a follow-up during the academic year and draw up a final evaluation report about the best practice – a complex experience, since work groups are heterogeneous, and the conditions at the venues where the APAE Programme develops (always close to the homes of students) are very uneven too.</p>
Results	<p>During the academic year 2015-2016, the programme took place in Alicante Town Council facilities located in five different quarters. The total number of primary- and secondary-education students to whom help was given amounted to 92, with a waiting list of another 32 minors who could not be included.</p> <p>The programme turns out to be enriching for both</p>

	<p>groups of participants; on the one hand, these minors benefit from the knowledge, values and experience of a mature teacher with another life perspective. And on the other hand, this activity enhances the collective role of teachers, because they play an active and fruitful role in society.</p> <p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The benefit in terms of the academic improvements for the students involved. Using the mostly positive scores from the first and last evaluation as a reference point to develop objective criteria. The families are highly satisfied too and wish to continue with the support programme during the next academic year. 2. The personal maturity level of these retired or pre-retired teaching staff, along with their more relaxed, lower-stress approach to life, positively influences both learning and value transmission, improving the teacher-student relationship too. 3. Teachers are volunteers motivated by a variety of personal and social interests, which has resulted in the availability of a highly-committed teaching staff. 4. The training and qualification level of the staff (mostly teachers/lecturers and graduates) was optimum for the classes taught. 5. As for the Social Action Department, the educators involved also described this resource as very necessary for many minors who need extra academic help. <p>These social educators referred more students than we could actually deal with, which clearly suggests the need to continue implementing the programme and looking for more volunteers as well as community centres where we can act.</p>
<p>Future perspectives</p>	<p>The APAE Programme is bound to grow in the future, and the challenge lies in trying to increase the number of volunteers involved in this programme. Another of the challenges is keeping a steady and large group of volunteers who can carry out substitution tasks if necessary.</p> <p>The participating institutions are also trying to</p>

	<p>improve the conditions needed in terms of infrastructure and teaching means, as well as the coordination level required to make this best practice easier and more convenient.</p>
<p>Remarkable facts</p>	<p>This programme –and best practice– has a high social impact and is always offered free of charge, and of course, on a non-profit basis. It additionally promotes intergenerational relationships and active ageing.</p> <p>Thanks to the APAE activity performed during the academic course 2015-2016, it was detected that the volunteer seniors involved stressed the need for greater attention and mentoring support. Thus, the UPUA and the School Absenteeism Department of the Alicante Town Council are permanently trying to drive an integral programme that can contribute to improve their mutual cooperation, focusing on such aspects as information supply and exchange, emotional support, better service quality, it all ultimately aimed at enhancing this best practice.</p>
<p>Bibliographic references</p>	<p>The Incubator of Values: http://www.universidadpermanente.com/iniciativas/en/content/general-presentation</p> <p>Protocol for action in educational centres. School Absenteeism Programme http://www.alicante.es/sites/default/files/documentos/documentos/absentismo-escolar/ab-protocolo-actuacion-centros.pdf</p> <p>http://www.alicante.es/es/noticias/educacion-impulsa-programa-intergeneracional-dar-clases-refuerzo-100-menores</p> <p>Betancor, A. <i>Integrando lo intergeneracional a la perspectiva del envejecimiento</i>. From: http://www.Academia.edu/download/30357386/archivo_1_id-83.Pdf</p> <p>Thoits, P. A., & Hewitt, L. N. (2001). Volunteer work and well-being. <i>Journal of Health and Social Behavior</i>, 42(2), 115-31. Retrieved from http://search.proquest.com/docview/201663945?accountid=17192</p>

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Best practices - concrete examples

9.2. BRATISLAVA

Financial learning and Financial literacy for seniors

Author/s	University of the Third Age, Centre for Continuing Education, Comenius University in Bratislava, Slovakia
Title	Financial learning and Financial literacy for seniors
Key words	Prevention of financial losses, knowledge and plan of own budget and finances, investments, care about personal money, usage of Internet banking
Context – location and impact	Course for seniors focused on financial learning realised at the University of the Third Age at Comenius University in Bratislava.
Start date	January 2014 – June 2017
Institutions involved	Centre for Continuing Education, UTA, Comenius University in Bratislava and Foundation for children of Slovakia
Thematic area	Overcoming the barriers and obtain confidence in the banks, bank products; Support of the elderly to prevent the financial losses, to learn more about their own finances,

	investments, how to prepare personal and family budget, how to care about money, usage of Internet banking
Justification	It is very important to show the older generation how important care about finances is. Therefore we want to show how important for daily life of the elderly the information about economy and finances are. It is necessary to give seniors a chance to learn new things and get new and actual information in chosen subject devoted to the financial learning
Objectives	<p>To offer knowledge in subject of economy and finance;</p> <p>To overcome barriers and obtain confidence in the banks and their employees; how to communicate with a bank;</p> <p>To encourage elderly in using the Internet banking;</p> <p>To show the elderly how to prepare budget; how to plan costs and incomes;</p> <p>To be careful in usage of credit/debit cards;</p> <p>To ensure good orientation in banks' products and practices;</p> <p>Objectives of saving money and having insurance.</p>
Experience and results	<p>The elderly involved in this programme were very thankful, showed big interest in the financial learning, usage of Internet banking, and knowing about banks' products and practices.</p> <p>They obtained new knowledge and new social contacts, became stronger in the communication with bank employees.</p> <p>The participants learned how to find new information, manage their own finances and costs and how to prepare personal and family budget.</p> <p>The participants found new friends and contacts in very friendly atmosphere of the financial course, which showed them that care about finances is not a stressful activity.</p>
Future perspectives	There are perspectives to continue in new themes and prepare continuing education on a higher level.

Remarkable facts	18 persons were involved in the course of financial learning in one period. There have already been 4 courses realised in duration of 5 month with 8 themes for learning (duration 2 hours each)
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Learning in the Communities

Author/s	University of the Third Age, Centre for Continuing Education, Comenius University in Bratislava
Title	Learning in the Communities
Key words	Support of the elderly and their inclusion in the education
Context – location and impact	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Námestovo – town in the North of Slovakia Centre for Continuing Education at Comenius University in Bratislava in the cooperation with the Elementary school and Municipality of the town Námestovo prepared a study offer for the first academic year in the course with general study content. Other 2 academic years have been devoted to the study of the subject “Man and health”. The number of participants increased from 35 to 104. The situation showed us interest of the elderly in this part of Slovakia, which is 350 km out of our capital, Bratislava. 2. Residential Home in Lamač, suburb of Bratislava Students of the University of the Third Age of

	Comenius University in Bratislava offered the lectures, free of charge, to the inhabitants of the residential home. First programme offered in 2016 was devoted to the general themes according to the possibilities of the elderly volunteers. Second programme in 2017 is offered by the University of the Third Age with the engagement of the university lecturers on historic topics.
Start date	September 2014 – June 2017
Institutions involved	Centre for Continuing Education Comenius University in Bratislava and town Námestovo; Residential Home in Lamač, Bratislava
Thematic area	Overcoming the barriers and educational support, Active ageing, Involvement of the elderly in rural areas and communities with the barriers and handicaps, Volunteering
Justification	It is very important to show other elderly and to wide population how the active ageing is important; To show how social inclusion can support health and proper opinions of the elderly on the life in the communities, families and society on the whole. To give chance disabled people learn new things and get new and latest information.
Objectives	To offer support for the communities which have difficulties to commute and take part in the educational activities nearby; To encourage the elderly to take part in learning and ensuring active aging; To overcome barriers and open space for those who have physical limits and cannot take part in the study programmes at university.
Experience and results	The elderly involved in this programme were very thankful, showed big interest in the lectures, in new knowledge and new social contacts; the participants learned how to find new information, manage own free time and engage other elderly from their surroundings. They found out new dimension in their life, new friends and contacts for

	the future cooperation and programmes.
Future perspectives	There are prospects to continue in new programmes but they need some enthusiastic persons who will organise and manage learning programmes and activities in this region or in the communities.
Remarkable facts	104 persons were involved in the rural area and other 20 seniors in the Residential Home. It means new 124 persons started to learn in their later life.
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Best practices - concrete examples

9.3. BRNO

Computer Literacy Courses

Author/s	University of the Third Age Brno University of Technology Czech Republic
Title	Computer Literacy Courses
Key words	Information technology, MS Windows, MS Office, world wide web, e-mail, search engines, digital photography, digital video processing, computer security, tablets, Android
Context – location and impact	Computer courses realized at the University of the Third Age at the Brno University of Technology

Start date	September 2014 – May 2017
Institution	University of the Third Age Brno University of Technology Czech Republic
Addressee	University of the Third Age Brno University of Technology
Thematic area	Computer literacy courses for seniors
Justification	For seniors, learning computers and internet skills it is not only for accessing information. It is the tool for keeping in touch with their family members, for presenting their life achievements etc.
Objectives	Through computer literacy courses students should learn basic principles of using MS Windows operation system, basic text processing skills. They are able to find and evaluate information on the web, to process digital photos and videos, to use mobile devices.
Experience	We use more pictures and fewer words in the handouts. We say the steps out loud and demonstrate on the projector for seniors. Many of the most popular applications can be enjoyed without reading or writing, just clicking or saying (search engines, translators etc.). Classes include twelve two-hours lessons (per semester) and may also include interactive demos, quizzes and assignments.
Results	Greater life satisfaction, develop an intuitive sense how computers work and how they can be used to make seniors life more efficient.
Future perspectives	To continue with new computer courses focused on new IT trends (voice recognition, mobile devices etc.).
Remarkable facts	More than 120 seniors enrolled to the computer courses each semester.

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Best practices - concrete examples

9.4. GRONINGEN

Co-operation in a regional network

Author/s	IJda Blüm, Albert Bos, Hedwig van den Brink, Peter Hug, Elma van Lier, Roelie Otter
Title	Co-operation in a regional network for fostering active participation of Elderly in society on a local base
Key words	Emancipation of the elderly, senior life style development
Context – location and impact	Training Elderly in the region to cope with changing macro-environmental factors. Emancipation to share societal responsibilities and self-management
Start date	May 2017
Institution	Senioren Academie Groningen-Friesland Drenthe
Thematic area	Changing roles and responsibilities of seniors due to rapid developments in society
Objectives	Contribute to the empowerment of the Elderly in co-operation with an organisation of older people

	(Denktank60+). Bringing the Senioren Academie nearer to the Elderly using e-learning where appropriate.
Experience	Preliminary discussions with Denktank60+Noord, a network of seniors
Results	<p>Work out plans for one or two courses in the context of a larger educational programme for the empowerment of the Elderly, in co-operation between Denktank60+ and Senioren Academie. The input of Denktank60+ is its experience in activating seniors, that of the Senioren Academie the presentation of scientific background .</p> <p>Subjects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -explaining the transition from welfare state to participation society -exploring demographic and social consequences for the region -designing possible models of participation for the elderly <p>E-learning could play an important role in the realisation.</p>
Future perspectives	Standard co-operation with Denktank60+Noord; extra promotion for courses of the Senioren Academie; sales potential for our (future) e-learning products
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Reconnaissance of e-learning

Author/s	IJda Blüm, Albert Bos, Hedwig van den Brink, Peter Hug, Elma van Lier, Roelie Otter
Title	Reconnaissance of e-learning
Key words	E-learning, digital recording
Context – location and impact	Making courses accessible for older people with restrictions. Broadening the group of potential students
Start date	December 2016
Institution	Senioren Academie Groningen-Friesland-Drenthe
Thematic area	E-learning
Objectives	<p>Bring adult learning nearer to people with digital recordings of courses and lectures. The following groups are specifically aimed at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Older people who wish to participate in courses but are hampered by physical handicaps or other obligations at the time of the lectures • Older people with lack of transport to the lecture hall • Participants who get ill during a course • Older people who prefer to make their own choice of when to study
Experience	Pilot recording of a lecture on 28 February 2017.
Results	<p>There are four different routes to make courses and lectures digitally available:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Real-time with interaction Direct broadcasting (e.g. via Livestream) to remote participants at home or to a group at a community centre. Remote participants can pose questions and take part in discussions via the online link. Strongly dependant on the quality of the local network on both sides. 2. Real-time without interaction As in 1. but no link from remote to lecture hall.

	<p>A simple setup could be with a fixed webcam in the lecture hall and transmission via Skype to a number of remote participants.</p> <p>3. Watching later on internet, no download Lectures are digitally recorded and edited offline. Made available for watching online on internet during a shorter or longer period.</p> <p>4. Download from internet or on DVD As in 3. but the recordings are for purchase as downloads or on DVD and can be watched offline anytime. Real-time transmission is not (yet) considered feasible.</p> <p>Recording for later watching can be done with 2 cameras (one fixed, one mobile) , one microphone and one laptop in the lecture hall, operated by 1 person. Material costs: € 1,300 – 1,500. If the technical installation in the lecture hall facilitates recording on SD cards, the laptop is not needed and costs decrease to € 600.</p> <p>Editing (mixing video pictures from the two cameras, sound from the microphone and pictures from PowerPoint presentations), is estimated to take 8 hours per lecture, using a simple program on a PC. Lectures could be available on internet after a few days.</p> <p>Hiring professional operators and editors would make e-learning financially unfeasible. Leaving the work to a group of technically experienced older volunteers could bring the costs down to an acceptable range.</p> <p>A fee can be asked for watching the recordings on internet (with a password) or for a purchase as a download or on DVD. With 10 customers per course a cost-covering price would be between € 30 and € 40. The exact pricing can only be established after a market research using some pilot recordings.</p>
Future perspectives	If financially and organisationally feasible digital recording could become standard practice for the

	majority of courses and lectures, thus making them accessible for a wider group of older people in the region and elsewhere.
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Co-operation of the Senioren Academie with the Senioren Sociëteit “De Remise” in Leeuwarden, Friesland

Author/s	Hedwig van den Brink, Peter Hug, IJda Blüm, Roelie Otter, Elma van Lier, Albert Bos
Title	Co-operation of the Senioren Academie with the Senioren Sociëteit “De Remise” in Leeuwarden, Friesland
Key words	Learning for older people, regional co-operation, own speed, familiar surroundings, digital means, e-learning
Context – location and impact	Promote new regional course programme for Elderly in Leeuwarden, Friesland
Start date	December 2016
Institution	Senioren Academie Groningen-Friesland-Drenthe Senioren Sociëteit “De Remise”, Leeuwarden
Thematic area	Promoting new course programmes and digital developments that correspond with the wishes of the Elderly. Bringing senior education nearer to the people.

Objectives	Bring learning for and by seniors nearer to the Elderly in their own familiar surroundings.
Experience	First pilot in February 2017: Offering the spring lecture of the Senioren Academie in Leeuwarden free of charge to members of “De Remise” to bring them in contact with the higher education for seniors offered by the Senioren Academie. Ten members accepted the offer.
Results	<p>Together with Mrs. Monique Medema, head of programme Leeuwarden of Senioren Academie, we have formulated the following targets:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Investigate ways to activate members of “De Remise” to attend courses of the Senioren Academie 2. Offer courses at the familiar surroundings of “De Remise” to those members that are mobile enough to get there. Maybe for a reduced course fee. 3. Offer the courses of the Senioren Academie in a digital form to members of “De Remise” and possibly other inhabitants who are less mobile. 4. Make the members of “De Remise” familiar with the regular educational programme of the Senioren Academie 5. As a first step offer free access to the spring lecture of the Senioren Academie in Leeuwarden.
Future perspectives	<p>Activate the members of “De Remise” to participate in senior education either at regular courses of the Senioren Academie, at the premises of “De Remise” or via internet at home.</p> <p>This will make membership of the Senioren Sociëteit more attractive and will bring extra course participants to the Senioren Academie.</p>
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Best practices - concrete examples

9.5. CHEMNITZ

Education of older people and cross-generational learning

Author	Technical University of Chemnitz, Institute for Pedagogy and Senior College
Title	Education of older people and cross-generational learning
Keywords	Educational excursions, Livestream, Cross- generational learning, Medial feedback systems in lectures, Usage of video telephony (Skype), Task- /Research groups in politics and product development
Context – Localization and Markup	<p>1. Educational excursions after lectures To deepen the knowledge, that was obtained through the presentations during subsequent educational excursions in practice (e.g. to research institutes, companies, cultural institutions and others)</p> <p>2. Broadcast via livestream of presentations on the Internet So that interested participants of every age, especially in rural regions without a University of the third age, are granted the possibility to participate in the presentations via livestream, either in groups or alone and are able to take part in the discussions</p> <p>3. Usage of video telephony (Skype) in the lecture hall for speakers (VIP) from other remote locations,</p>

to transmit their presentation (Power-Point-Presentation and speech) to two large presentation surfaces

4. Use of Feedback-Apps on smartphones and tablets of the attendees in the lecture hall to immediately display the analysed answers to questions/opinions

5. Two Erasmus+projects “EDUSENET” and “Elderly People built together with Younger People Bridges for Europa” (2015-2017) with presentation for members of the European Parliament (CULT) in Strassbourg 2017 and a Transfer Conference in June 2017 in Chemnitz with experts and seniors from 10 countries

6. Cross-generational learning in the seniors’ partnership programme for international students
About 10 seniors look after about 20 international students, mostly from India, China and other distant countries within the scope of a partnership programme. The goal is to improve the German language skills of the students, the mediation of German culture, visits to museums and institutions, encounters with intergenerational discussions in clubs. Vice versa the seniors improve their foreign language skills, intercultural competencies and their knowledge about other cultures

7. Task groups for activation and research:

7.1. Innovation circle for technical optimization of kitchenware and kitchen furniture

Seniors, students, scientists and employees of companies are working cross-generational in this innovation circle to further develop kitchenware and kitchen furniture up to patent application

7.2. Task group Politics

In the task group Politics Seniors are working on analyses of implemented activities and electoral programmes of big parties in the Bundestag. The results are presented in an event in front of 700 seniors in the Senior College (Seniorenkolleg) to convey competent neutral political-scientific comparative information to aid the seniors with their election decisions

Starting Date	November 2014 – April 2017
Institution	Technical University of Chemnitz, Institute for Pedagogy and Senior College
Topics	Reduction of Barriers and support of the education of elders, Active Ageing, Medially supported education (livestream, video telephony, feedback systems) for older people from rural regions, Cross-generational innovative research work in the fields of technology and politics
Authorization	<p>Expansion of the number of older education participants by reduction of inhibition thresholds and increase of the offers for elders in rural regions.</p> <p>Application oriented excursions in practice as additions to the knowledge-based presentations at the University</p> <p>Development and improvement of cross-generational learning with the help of a seniors' partnership programme with international students which holds mutual benefits for the generations</p> <p>Involvement of seniors and students in research activity together with researchers and representatives of companies for technical optimization up to patent application and for political education and advice of and for older people</p>
Goals	<p>Development of optimized low-threshold educational offers for elders in urban and rural regions</p> <p>Expansion of medial education by using livestream broadcasts of presentations with discussions, video telephony, feedback apps</p> <p>Development of new forms of cross-generational education and encounters between German seniors and international students in the framework of a partnership programme</p> <p>Application oriented excursions in practice as additions to knowledge-based learning and involvement in cross-generational collaborations</p>

	regarding research projects together with the industry and for political education and consulting as well as cooperation with seniors' delegations
Experience	<p>The number of older participants in the educational offers of the Senior College (Seniorenkolleg) did increase further. The participants are grateful for the transfer of knowledge and recommendations for application in everyday life (PC- and information technology, technical support, cultural and political education, health education, financial investments and others)</p> <p>The education of older people is at the same time a contribution to the promotion of social encounters with many other elders who live alone and with young students who are instructors for courses and support the organization of the educational programme.</p> <p>The European cooperations with older people from different European countries are being increasingly appreciated as an important exchange of information and experience with reciprocal stimulations and the active participation in these Erasmus programmes is increasing. Elders are more and more interested in the preservation and the advancement of the European Union.</p>
Results	Individual results see final report booklet and project homepage
Future Prospects	Expansion of education of older people and especially of the cross-generational education with younger people as well as the expansion of the accompanying research regarding the educational programmes and European projects with and for older people as well as intergenerational
Notable Facts	<p>Out of 162 survey participants only 16 % were from villages, the rest were from small towns or large cities.</p> <p>More educational offers with low inhibition thresholds are necessary in rural regions - possibly transferred medially</p>

Literature References	see booklet
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Best practices - concrete examples

9.6. MAGDEBURG

Initial question: How do we attract new members to Senior Studies? *(Olaf Freyemark, 13.03.2017)*

The project managers have considered various ways to attract fresh members to the Lifelong Learning 50+ program. A first consideration was to approach retirement homes and draw the attention of senior citizens to our 50+ program. We visited various administration units of senior housing facilities in Magdeburg. The board members' response to our plans to present our 50+ program in retirement homes was a positive one. The management of two retirement facilities even made conference rooms available to deliver our lectures and presentations.

How would be the intellectual output of this approach evaluated? There has been no significant interest in our 50+ program. Only few participants came to our opening program presentation. No significant number of people attended the events afterwards as well.

The organizers quickly realized that this is not the right way to provoke interest to Senior Studies. Among the conclusions we arrived at were that

retirement home residents have come to an age when they are mostly concerned with themselves and/or restricted by various disabilities.

Another approach yielded a greater response. The program managers wrote to some representatives of District Senior Councils within the Federal Region of Saxony Anhalt. It was planned to present the 50+ program during usual meetings. The meeting partakers were assumed to play a multiplier function by speaking about the opportunity of 50+ program participation at various places, aiming to attract fresh participants. So, we took part at meetings of District Senior Councils in Stendal, Haldensleben, Genthin, Gommern, Schoenebeck and Halberstadt. There was actually a genuine interest at all the places we were in touch with. The 50+ program was presented and first questions were discussed. The sharing of experiences was a win-win situation for both parties. The program managers were given insight into the work of volunteers. Their work was influenced by the fact that they represented the interests of senior citizens and stood up for their values. It became clear that the discussed issues were extremely diverse considering elderly care, pension rates, improved housing infrastructure and other everyday life issues. On the other hand, the representatives of the Senior Councils gained insight into certain academic standards in the area of scientific research and continuous education. The actual demand for senior education was acknowledged. It was agreed that education contributes to a healthy way of living, a self-determined life and active participation in public activities.

During the discussions it became clear that the topic of senior education should be strongly addressed in the future. Everyone must be aware of the fact that education is to be considered an integral part of all life cycles.

One-off event could not be considered sufficient. Above all, social groups with lower academic qualification had been approached. The 65+ group was clearly committed to continuous education, because of their higher academic qualification. Persons with lower vocational qualification were less interested to discuss education topics, after having reached a certain age.

Best practice 1: Hands on Media

Author	Karin Braune
Experience	New Media, Senior Citizens and Internet, Movie
Context - Placement and Impact	The setting of an online group was initiated by employees collaborating on the internet referred to as the <i>Magdeburg hemispheres</i> . Under the motto 'Loving and Aging' the group realized various projects, such as the creation of a radio play, a short video as well as a picture collage. The presentation of the project took place at the Annual Conference of Media Education in Erfurt.
Starting Date	2013
Institution	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Audience	Senior and regular students, media interested
Topic Area	Set-up an online platform and an online group; perform a radio play, produce videos, design a poster project "Meet the New Media", New Media multigenerational interaction
Authorized Access	Open to all participants of Lifelong Learning 50+
Objective	The interaction between the young and elderly participants is to be intensified by collaborating with the new media. Prejudices between the generations are to be tackled that way. Collaborative efforts are to be performed aiming to provide evidence that elderly participants can also interact with new media.
Experience	Young and elderly participants collaborate and successfully submit an assignment together. The application of new media is therefore intensified.
Intellectual Output	Online platform, videos, sharing experiences between young and elderly participants.
Prospects	Mastering an approach for a joint study of young and elderly students. Several generations share their experiences and learn from each other.

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Best practice 2: Grass Art Project

Author	Anne Facius
Experience	Grass, Nature, Art, Craft work
Context - Placement and Impact	The grassy worlds, meandering in the summer breeze, fascinated me and aroused my creative curiosity. The idea of using grass as a design material came to me when I looked at a meadow of reddish-purple grass along the mountain field. Depending on location, soil and climate conditions, the grass would shine in pink, violet or green color. I wanted to capture this splendor, to hold it in my arms and use it for my artistic work.
Starting Date	2014
Institution	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Empfänger	Senior students, art interested participants, nature fans
Topic Area	Grass along mountain fields and meadows, studio discussions, design exhibitions at the Havelberg National Garden Show and the International Garden Show in Berlin.
Authorized Access	Open to all participants of Lifelong Learning 50+
Objective	The main intent is to use grass as a medium to

	design wall carpets, coats and hats. Long walks in the nature are also intended to be performed.
Experience	Motto of the events 'With joy and friends together we actively grow old'.
Intellectual Output	Art objects
Prospects	Bring art closer to other interested people
Contact Data	
Website	www.meb.ovgu.de

Best practice 3: Writing workshop

Author	Dr. Gabriele Czech
Title	Writing workshop
Experience	Literary works and writing, European culture, relevant values.
Context - Placement and Impact	In the years 2008 to 2010, the Chair of Adult Education at the Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg was a partner within a European-wide project of the EFOS (European Association of Senior Students at Universities). The Project intent was to promote cultural traditions and regional values of their own countries by means of focusing on specific topics, e.g. literary texts, customs and rituals, reading habits through the lens of interculturalism within the framework of the common European cultural background. In this context the intergenerational aspect left a significant benchmark. The writing workshop was also in vogue within continuous education and research as a collaborative framework.
Starting Date	2014
Institution	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Empfänger	Senior students, participants interested in literature and writing

Topic Area	Literature, interculturalism, European culture and values in literary fiction; these topics should bring together young and elderly participants to discuss relevant values.
Authorized Access	Open to all participants of Lifelong Learning 50+
Objective	The objective is to bring cultural traditions and values of their own countries, focusing on specific topics, such as literary texts, customs and rituals, and reading habits. This project intends to initiate research under the lead of interculturalism and common European background.
Experience	Understanding European culture und literature
Intellectual Output	Writing personal narratives
Prospects	Encourage the sharing of literary experience based on relevant values.

Best practice 4: Project on intergenerational witnesses

Author	Dr. habil. Kerstin Dietzel
Title	A project on intergenerational witnesses in everyday life; the Zero Hour living conditions of the Magdeburg residents (1945)
Experience	Intergenerational learning, witness disclosure and research, witness narratives
Context - Placement and Impact	From March 2014 to April 2016 a student group from the senior studies at the Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg, together with students of the Magdeburg Stendal University of Applied Sciences worked on an intergenerational test project under the scientific guidance of Dr. Kerstin Dietzel. Intergenerational as a term means that regular and senior students collaborate together as a team on a research project.
Starting Date	2014

Institution	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Empfänger	Senior and regular students, witnesses, historians, museums and city archives.
Topic Area	Everyday life and living conditions of Magdeburg residents during the Zero Hour (1945), witness research, interviews.
Authorized Access	Open to all participants of Lifelong Learning 50+
Objective	The objective is to tap sources of modern history which are to be used to design an exhibition on everyday life and living conditions of the Magdeburg population during the Zero Hour. The main research is focused on food supply during 1945 in Magdeburg as well as the housing situation.
Experience	Historical research
Intellectual Output	Witness research
Prospects	Exploring historical background and making it available to the next generations.
References	Margaret Brüinig, Olaf Freymark, Ursel Hartmann, Dr. Ute Kaden, Dr. Iris Paasche, Barbara Schiller, Dr. Eckart Sickel, Sarita Sowka, and Kristina Ziegler were among the research fellows within the senior studies group.

Best practice 5: Digital Photography, Creative design with Adobe Photoshop

Author	Ulrich Arendt and Sylvia Beer
Experience	Digital photography, photo exhibition, image editing
Starting Date	2015
Institution	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Audience	Senior and regular students

Topic Area	Photography, Magdeburg, parks, urban ambience, the Elba; creative graphics and image design
Authorized Access	Open to all participants of Lifelong Learning 50+
Objective	<p>The objective is to develop a concept how to design and implement a photo exhibition in Magdeburg. It is planned first to take photos at various locations in Magdeburg. Then pictures will be creatively processed and designed for an exhibition.</p> <p>The objective is to acquire professional experience with relevant editing tools on different levels, filling and setting levels on PC during image processing. Finally, it is all about creative image design.</p>
Experience	Shooting and processing pictures to evidence the city perception of Magdeburg. Photography, image design
Intellectual Output	Photos, exhibition
Prospects	Image processing should advance to the next level of creative design.

Best practice 6: 'Hike knowingly' – International hiking group

Author	Dr. Heidrun Guericke
Experience	Regional environment, regional history, hiking tours, sharing experiences
Starting Date	2015
Institution	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Audience	Senior students from various academic institutions in Groningen, Hannover, Bielefeld und Magdeburg.
Topic Area	Regional history and geography, hiking tours, countryside and people
Authorized	Open to all participants of Lifelong Learning 50+

Access	
Objective	The objective is to perform hiking tours around the region having gained a regional insight in advance. Lectures on various topics are to be presented and discussed. During hiking tours significant historical places and natural sightseeing environments are to be explored.
Experience	Sharing experiences, bringing history back to life.
Prospects	Continuous sharing of experiences, defining new hiking locations and itineraries.

Best practice 7: Sharing experiences between senior students

Author	Olaf Freymark
Title	Sharing experiences between senior students of the Senior Academy Groningen and the Lifelong Learning 50+ program at the Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Experience	Regional environment, sharing experiences, discussion on various topics: politics, relevant values, demography, culture and regions.
Starting Date	2015
Institution	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
Audience	Senior students from Groningen / Netherlands and Magdeburg.
Topic Area	Regional history, countryside and people, literature, politics, sociology.
Authorized Access	Open to all participants of Lifelong Learning 50+
Objective	The objective is to promote a continuous sharing of experiences between the two countries. It covers the exploration of various topics such as: literature, history, witnesses, politics and regions. It is focused on a better understanding and regular

	exchange of opinions.
Experience	Sharing experiences.
Prospects	Continuous sharing of experiences.
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Best practices - concrete examples

9.7. UPPSALA

Recruitment project aiming at persons with varying cultural background

Uppsala has quite a number of people born in countries with varying culture. They are, however, not well represented amongst the members of USU. Our ambition is to engage a greater number of people with varying cultural background in our different activities to the benefit of all parties involved. We would like to engage them as members, as co-operators and as teachers/lecturers. A number of efforts have been introduced in order to achieve a positive result.

We started by contacting several organisations where we could find people from the groups that we were targeting, organisations like Families for International Friendship, The Uppsala Language School, The school for adult education and some organisations for immigrants. We visited also activities attended by many immigrants. And we took individual contacts. To make it easier for people to take part in our activities we had to our disposal an allowance from the board of USU to facilitate the engagement for some individuals. The response from our target group was unfortunately not overwhelming. We had to find other methods.

The project we are now preparing is a series of lectures entitled "Music from all over the world". In six different lectures we are aiming to present music from one country/region per lecture with the participation of people originating from the country/region in question. These persons are familiar with the music theoretically as well as have skills to play different instruments and perform themselves. This coming autumn our programme consists of music lectures from Morocco, Ireland, Japan, South America, Bulgaria and Persia. In order to prepare for a wide spread participation of people we will make contact with different immigrant organisations. We hope that the programme will engage a great variety of people whose mixed cultural backgrounds will create interesting meetings.

Contact person: Dr Ulla Myhrman; Uppsala Senioruniversitet

Filmed lectures available via the website of Uppsala Senioruniversitet - a pilot project to reach new groups of seniors

Per Olof Osterman, MD, PhD. Project leader

Summary

22 lectures given by Uppsala Senioruniversitet (USU) in 2016 were filmed. The project aimed at facilitating for members to participate in the lectures offered. The films were stored on a server for 14 days and could be viewed by streaming but not downloaded and saved. Members logged in to see the films via the website of USU. There were some technical difficulties but 21 films could be shown. 23 to 96 members (average 56) logged in to view each film. About 15% were 80 years or older, the oldest being 93. A majority were women and in about the same proportion as those attending the lectures. In a residential home 5 - 20 members watched the films together on a big screen and in addition several also watched them individually. Filming of selected lectures now continues as a permanent activity of USU.

Purpose of the project

The project aimed at reaching new groups for membership at USU by facilitating for members to participate in the lectures offered. The target groups were:

- Members who are disabled, including those living in residential homes, and have difficulties in attending the lecture hall.

- Members who live far from Uppsala
- Members who are occupied or not in town when the lecture is given
- Members who did participate but after the lecture want to repeat what was said

Methods and technique

The USU board approved the pilot project in November 2015. The decision was founded on an analysis of the organizational, technical and economical prerequisites. The project was not to be implemented if many future lecturers would be negative to filming. Therefore an inquiry of 67 previous lecturers was performed about their willingness to accept filming if they were to give future lectures. A proposed agreement was attached. 61% (41) responded. Only two would refuse filming. Two were uncertain and positive only if the fee was raised.

Technique

The power point pictures projected from the speaker's lap top were imported to the video film. In this project the lap tops of the speaker and

film producer were communicating wirelessly via a router. A BlackMagic converter was used to digitalize the video signals from the film camera.

The sound was picked up from the audio system of the lecture hall or via a microphone and a Wirecast video software from Telestream was used for production of the video. Total cost of the equipment was about 5000 €.

The video produced was uploaded to a server (Vimeo) and for 14 days it could be viewed by streaming but not downloaded or saved.

Training of film team

The assistance of Simon Ydhag, (MedfarmDoIT, Office for Medicine and Pharmacy, Uppsala University), was invaluable both for the choice of equipment, training of the film team and good advice for solving technical problems during the beginning of the project period.

Film picture from a lecture about art showing the lecturer and the PP picture simultaneously. The film producer could choose to record like this, or fill the screen with only the PP picture or the speaker.

Access to the films by members

Two kinds of lectures were filmed. The so called Tuesday lectures, given every fortnight, are free for all members. Eight lectures were filmed in the spring and eight in the autumn of 2016. All members of the USU could log in to see the films via the website of the USU and "My pages". A series of six lectures about the biological evolution were filmed in the autumn of 2016. Only members who had paid the special fee for attending the lectures could log in and see these films.

Agreement with lecturers

A written agreement was made with the lecturers regulating the use of the filmed material. USU agreed not to use the filmed material in other contexts and to keep it available to watch for members no longer than 14 days.

Follow-up methods

Scanning was used to register those members who participated in Tuesday lectures. The member-id, sex and age of the attendants at each lecture therefore is known. No such registration was made for the series about the evolution. Registration was made of all members who logged in and started the films. In the spring of 2016 a survey was made among 40 members of the USU living in a residential home, Ekeby Hus. Members there were both watching the films together on a big screen and individually at home. The number watching together was registered.

Results and experience

Technical problems

The procedure of connecting the different units was more complex and sensitive to disturbances than expected. The film team met various problems, many of which concerned sound uptake and spent many hours of training and problem solving. One of the first films was a failure, a few had not so good quality, mostly due to sound problems, but most films were very good. The technical problems were mastered by the end of the project period and those who watched the films expressed their contentment with the project and film quality.

Tuesday lectures

Between 30 and 96 individuals (mean 65) logged in to watch each film. Of the individuals who listened to the lectures live in the autumn of 2016 about 10% afterwards logged in to watch a film.

Among the about 3,800 members of the USU 2/3 are women. In the *spring of 2016* a mean of 277 members participated (179 - 443) in Tuesday lectures and of these 61% were women. Of those who logged in to watch films from these lectures 59% were women, i.e. a similar sex distribution. In the *autumn of 2016* a mean of 203 members participated (126 - 321) and also now 61% of these and 59% of those who logged in to watch films were women.

Lecture series about the evolution

192 members payed the fee for participation. The number of persons actually attending each lecture is not known but usually 10 - 15% are absent. Between 23 and 51 individuals (mean 34) logged in to watch each film. Thus a mean of 18% of the participants of the series used the possibility to see the films.

Age distribution of those watching films

This could only be evaluated for Tuesday lectures and was similar in the spring and autumn. About 15% were 80 years or older, the eldest being 93.

Films watched at the residential home Ekeby Hus

At this residential home 5 - 20 members watched the films together on a big screen and in addition several also watched individually in their homes. In the inquiry mentioned above 28 (70%) of the 40 members of USU living at Ekeby Hus responded. At the time of the inquiry only four films had been shown. 16 of 28 would not have seen the lecture if it had not been filmed. 20 wanted USU to continue the film project, 6 did not know. 15 wanted USU to add some series of lectures (only Tuesday lectures were filmed in the spring 2016).

Future perspectives

Filming of lectures is appreciated among the members and now considered an established activity which continues at USU. Filming enables members who are disabled to take part in lectures and allows members to watch the lecture at a time they choose. The statistics also show that members use the possibility to see films to repeat what has been said at the lecture. It is too early to tell if the filming will attract new members who live at a long distance from Uppsala. Many small Senior universities have difficulties in recruiting good lecturers whereas Uppsala with two universities can offer good education to the members. A future cooperation with distribution of filmed lectures to these smaller U3A's could be considered.

Participants

Film team: Lasse Sunnås, team leader, Bengt Everitt, Bo Olsson, Anders Lundström, *Website functions:* Bertil Eriksson

Contact details

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10. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From surveys from the partners of the project we come to the following general conclusions:

- There are considerable differences between the different U3As in terms of organization, economy, history, age of students etc. We would thus firstly say that each U3A will have to cope with its development work and improvement according to its own context and what has been brought forward as results from the different surveys.
- Secondly there are many situations which are similar where U3As can learn from each other.
- Thirdly we will highlight problems and situations which have to be dealt with by politicians and decision makers throughout Europe.

More specific but common conclusions from surveys are the following:

- There is a considerable potential of seniors who would like to go on learning but have not (yet) attended courses for various reasons;
- Learning at higher age is good for wellbeing and engagement in society;
- Most heard hindrances: costs, distance and public transport to course venue, health problems;
- Seniors in remote areas prefer to get courses in their vicinity. The course should be brought nearer to the people by decentralising course venues to regional centres, housing organisations;
- The most important motives for Elderly to take part in senior education are ‘Finding out things and acquiring new knowledge” and “Meeting people and improving social contacts”;
- A considerable part of the seniors are open to the use of new technologies and internet but need training.

Problems and situations to be dealt with:

In the face of the positive development of higher average life expectancies and the growing rate of older people over 60 in the European Union with: 2015: 25%; 2030: 31%; 2050: 34%; the role of the elderly in society has to be re-evaluated.

The current social development leads the way from a deficient towards a positive conception of age.

Deficient conception of age: Older people are mostly seen as a burden for the younger ones and the society as a consequence of their shortcomings. Elderly are often being discriminated, e.g. by establishing calendrical age limits. There is little funding of projects for and with Elderly and their efforts are not appreciated.

Positive conception of age: Older people are more and more being seen as a positive and active part of society that forms and further develops society together and on equal footing with all generations without calendrical age limits.

- Retirement should be looked upon in its new context, not as something necessary for all when work/labour was so hard that very few people were able to continue after a certain age. Work has changed and so should “not work”. Most of us enjoy to do something, to mean something and to find a meaning in life. Now many seniors do go into a crisis because of loss of identity at retirement, as retirement means more a mental loss than freedom. If life becomes too still the brain seems to have the capacity to develop fears which are not real and not easy to handle. – “*If a bicycle stops it will fall*”.

This is also illustrated by the answers of the questionnaire when people say that they themselves have to overcome some psychological obstacles to engage themselves in new learning activities after retirement.

- We need a new way of research on ageing, where also seniors are actively engaged. What is presented in this report is a humble step in this direction. We seniors can contribute even if we have not got the economic resources and works at a slower speed. At the same time it will give us a chance to be seen and listened to to get the evidence that we *exist* and still learn even if we perhaps learn in another way than young people. We do not learn facts as easy and do not remember all of them the same way as we used to do – but at the same time we have the capacity of integrating new knowledge with old knowledge and experience which helps us to understand complex situations and perhaps come up with other alternative ideas than young people do. We still have no way to measure in a scientific way if it is like this but we hope for someone who will do research on it and develop instruments for it.

- Work has traditionally (Taylorism) been measured as time. What would happen if work was more measured in terms of results? Perhaps this would suit better as seniors who could then concentrate on good results and not on the time spent as young people do. From a survey in Uppsala (USU) it is reported that out of 188 seniors 28% had wanted to continue with the job they had - either fully or partly - but were forced to retire. (USU report no. 14. 2012)

A discussion has now started about the future labour market and different models for it, where perhaps even seniors could fit in. We need to ask new questions which are not based on old thinking and traditional division between labour and what is now “not labour”/retirement.

- Existing research results about how working processes for older people and cross-generational, benefitting all parties, are supposed to be further developed, are not being implemented sufficiently in practice. At the moment there are numerous research results regarding work structuring for and with older people, but they are not known widely enough and most importantly they are hardly implemented in practice
- These important aspects of an ageing society show the necessity for the European Union, the state government and the municipalities to encourage and materially support the education of older people and cross-generational education with younger people. Currently the funding is more orientated towards younger people at school, in training or university. This is important but the funding has to be used beneficially for all generations and complemented and expanded through cross-generational education and support programmes. By implementing cross-generational cooperation with older people it is possible to e.g. reduce school failure and dropping out of school or to reduce the lengthening of time spent in university or dropping out of university.
- The described development opportunities with a change to a positive view of elderly form a good social background for understanding and

interpreting the results of the EduSenNet-project and for designing recommendations.

- Retirement age regulations may be practical from an administrative point of view but “elderly” as a concept is a social construction. We elderly carry with us our capabilities and experiences throughout life, and even though our power and energy may decline with age, society cannot afford not to make full use of all the knowledge and experience held by the entire population - including seniors.

We seniors are more than just taxpayers and voters at elections. For a continuous development of the idea of democracy in the society we all need lifelong learning as a basis for taking active participation. The great political challenge in a country where many reach a high age must be to find ways of strengthening elderly people’s capacity to cope with new situations, to find consistency and meaning in life, and thus also ensure that they remain in good health. We would thus stress the importance of lifelong learning as a means to empower seniors to participate actively in democratic and political processes in the society.

11. SUMMARY

The EduSenNet project focuses on the specific needs of learners aged over 50 and on the conditions under which they learn. The project examines the extent of possible innovation, how it may be undertaken and for whom. Researchers from 7 universities in 6 European countries have been working together to find the best possible ways of helping older people to satisfy their learning needs in the later years of their working life and during retirement. All project meetings have been dedicated to presentation of the project work, coordination of the results, analysis and evaluation of the project progress to assign tasks for the next working phase. We have realised 6 transnational meetings combined with training of the elderly students, brainstorming discussions and 3 workshops focusing on universities for seniors as a social task of each society, intergenerational learning and e-learning. The final conference “Education for the elderly and young people in Europe” was organised by the partner at the Technical University in Chemnitz with the participation of 160 elderly students and project partners from 2 Erasmus+ projects: “Educational Senior Network – EduSenNet” and project „Elderly build bridges together with young people in Europe“.

At the beginning of the project questionnaires were created to get a view on the learning needs, to get to know the opinions of elderly and senior students who were contacted as target groups. Their input was of major importance and was used for the development of the pedagogical innovations, evaluation and description of good practices. A multi-method approach was used for the realisation of the project tasks and analysis with a predominance of qualitative techniques. These sought to verify the achieved goals and the learning competences acquired (through the focus groups of elderly, study programmes and their innovations, new individuals and groups of involved seniors, etc.).

Quantitative techniques were also used when we analysed the responses of the respondents. The group of the elderly respondents consisted of 930 persons, whom we contacted and interviewed in various communities. The group of elderly students whom we interviewed at universities and senior academies consisted of 3,151 persons. This means that in our project EduSenNet we questioned 4,081 elderly persons from 7 countries

(Czech Republic, Germany, The Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Spain and Sweden). During the project period the seven project teams regularly met to discuss their project approaches, realisation of the project tasks, ways of the communication with the respondents as well as to give presentations of the project findings and results. The project booklet describes besides the project researches also the theoretical framework, working methods and possibilities for innovations. Chapter 9 is devoted to the description of the best practices as good examples from the learning process and meaningful leisure time activities for the elderly. The project partners have described 17 best practices, but some partners did work on other innovations too. Encouraging initiatives are taken in the field of:

- E-learning (Uppsala, Groningen)
- Live stream of lectures on Internet and Feedback system in lectures with smartphones (Chemnitz)
- Decentralising course venues through cooperation with societies of older people, in residential homes, rural areas (Alicante, Bratislava, Groningen, Uppsala)
- Collaborative learning schemes – peer to peer training and voluntary service initiatives (Alicante)
- Creative learning schemes – digital photography, digital video, creative design and art, creative writing (Bratislava, Brno, Magdeburg)
- Intergenerational learning in all partners' institutions
- Collaborative learning activities in collaboration with municipalities (Alicante, Bratislava)

For the project dissemination we have created our own website (<http://edusennet.efos-europa.eu/>), 7 Newsletters and a project flyer. We also published 2 booklets with the research and project results. Thanks to the Erasmus+ programme of the European Commission we have been able to carry out this research on lifelong learning in the field of senior education at Universities of the Third Age (U3As) / Academies in Europe, which is very often on the edge of public interest and needs to draw more attention with new information that can be presented, disseminated, published and discussed.

Nadežda Hrapková, project coordinator / president of EFOS (European Federation of Older Students in Universities)

Transnational meeting in Brno 17.- 19. April 2015

Transnational meeting in Alicante 28. – 30. September 2016

Transnational meeting in Uppsala 28. – 30. April 2016

Transnational meeting in Magdeburg 3. - 5. November 2016

APAE Programme: 'Support to the prevention of school absenteeism'
Best practices from UPUA Alicante Spain

Activities in the communities from Bratislava

